

**COMPARATIVE GENOME AND PROTEOME
ANALYSIS OF *Catla catla* FROM HALDA RIVER**

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Abstract

Catla catla is an important Indian Major Carp found in the inland water bodies of Bangladesh. It contributes a lot to the country's aquaculture system. Halda River is a unique natural habitat for this fish, where it gets the favorable physicochemical factors during monsoon for the natural spawning procedure while naturally spawned eggs of this fish are collected and sold as well. For a better understanding towards this species regarding its physiology, behavior, ecology and conservation aspects, the whole genome sequence was revealed and at scaffold level assembly (GCA_014525385.1) was reported recently. Based on the genomic data sets available in global NCBI sites, we attempted a comparative analysis of the genome and proteome by achieving the chromosome level genome assembly during this study. Later we compared it with other closely related cyprinid species. A chromosome level genome was constructed with 25 pair chromosomes, and the genome was less fragmented (total 2225 sequences), with a relatively large N50 (33.39 Mbp) and had a total of 1059564832 base pairs. Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs (BUSCO) refer to the completeness of 93.8% (Eukaryota) and 92.2% (Actinopterygii) of the assembled genome and 24% of repeat elements were found on the genome. A total of 49028 genes were predicted and 35572 genes were functionally annotated. *C. catla* shared 25860 clusters with four other cyprinid species and possessed 19973 singleton genes for which no orthologs could be found in any of the other species. Further analyses can explore the unique proteomics signatures in *Catla* which will help elucidate the unique features of this species.

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Chapter 01

Introduction

Despite being a relatively small country, Bangladesh has a rich biodiversity as it is a part of the Indo-Burma biodiversity hotspot (Stanford 1991). But biodiversity loss is now a global issue and Bangladesh too is not excluded from that problem. To face the adversities of biodiversity loss, the ecological and economic role of a species must be well understood and in that case revelation of genome sequence of a species can greatly be advantageous. Taking account of the situation, several whole genome sequences of native species were revealed previously. Most recently the whole genome sequence of *Catla catla*, a native Indian Major Carp (IMC) was revealed. This work largely targets the genome assembly of *C. catla* up to the chromosome level, functional genome analysis, quantitative trait loci analysis, and genome-wide association study (GWAS) and Pathway analysis of economically important traits.

1.1 Background

Of the main vertebrate groupings, fishes are the most numerous and diversified. Through a stunning array of morphological, physiological, and behavioral adaptations, they rule the world's oceans. The huge number of fish species still alive is a reflection of their variety. According to fishbase, as of February 2022, there are 33,230 species of fish with reliable descriptions, although the true number is probably closer to 34,000. Around 4250 species (12.79%) of fish belong to the order Cypriniformes and *Catla catla* is one of the most discernible species of the order Cypriniformes (Fishbase, 2022).

Fish live in a wide variety of environments. They thrive in seasonal ponds, sporadic streams, small desert springs, the wide ranges of the open oceans, deep oceanic depths, frigid mountain streams, saline coastal inlets and fjords, and a seemingly limitless variety of aquatic conditions. This means that fish can live at temperatures ranging from -1.8°C to almost 40°C , in water with pH values ranging from 4 to 10 or above and dissolved oxygen levels ranging from close to zero to saturation, in salinity levels ranging from 0 to 90 ppt, and at depths of up to 7,000 m under the immense pressure of the water column (Davenport and Sayer 1993). Fish are ectothermic animals, typically with vertebral column, gills, and fins, and they rely primarily on water as a medium for survival (Lagler, 1977).

Fish, in general, have substantially more phenotypic variety than other vertebrates; huge differences in growth rates, body size, color patterns, and other characteristics are prevalent both between and within populations. Because most

fish are quite plastic in their capacity to adjust to favorable or unfavorable environmental conditions, most of this diversity is connected to the environment (Moyle and Cech, 2004).

However, there is growing recognition that this phenotypic variability has a genetic ground and that genotypic variety is necessary to preserve it. Lately, a genetic rationale for variety in features including life-history patterns, color patterns, migration capacity, tolerance to low pH and pollutants, disease resistance and shoaling behavior has been discovered in fishes. In general, fish with high heterozygosity i.e. having several alleles for a particular trait are more likely to have offspring that reproduce, particularly in a fluctuating environment (Carvalho, 1993).

Most of the bony fish fossils are retrieved from freshwater which suggests that much of their evolutionary accomplishment is related to the freshwater environment. In contrast with the condition of bony fishes, the cartilaginous fishes (chondrichthyes) fossils are discovered from marine deposits and they first appeared in the fossil record more than 400 million years ago, and during the Devonian period, they were widespread. Later on, the chondrichthyes evolved into two different evolutionary lines in the Devonian period which are the subclasses Holocephali (chimeras) and Elasmobranchii (sharks and rays). The elasmobranchs first appeared in the middle Devonian and ever since they remain one of the apex predators in the oceans. The chimaeras first appeared in the upper Devonian and are invertebrate-feeding, bottom-dwelling fishes. The group Acanthodii (spiny sharks), oldest known jawed vertebrates that lived around 440 million years ago, is thought to be a sister group of bony fishes (Nelson, 1994).

It is well known that DNA is the blueprint of life, while evolution is the architect of that blueprint. Among the vertebrate groups, fishes have triumphed through a long path of evolution which is around 530 million years. This long evolutionary history shaped the fate of modern fishes and resulted in a monumental number of fish species with unique genetic features, and within each species are thousands or millions of genetically unique individuals. In recent decades, scientists have learned to read the DNA blueprint and have begun to unravel the history recorded within. From family pedigrees to the most ancient vertebrate lineages, can be explained, resolved by genetic investigations (Helfman, 2009). Between these two extremes, genetic surveys are valuable for detecting new species as well as clarifying biogeographic patterns and conservation management units. There are several subspecialties within genetics. Cytogenetics, for example, is the study of chromosomes, while ecological genetics can reveal breeding behavior, population genetics is used to define stock management units for

fisheries, evolutionary genetics demonstrates the basis of novel organismal traits, and molecular phylogenetics is the use of DNA data to resolve branches in the tree of life. Genomics is the study of an organism's complete DNA sequence, which includes both the smaller mitochondrial genome and the huge nuclear genome, which may include over a billion base pairs (bp). The first investigations into fish genomics were chromosomal counts and karyotypes, but genomics currently generally refers to the rigorous attempts to record the full nuclear genome for many species. The technology used in the Human Genome Project was targeted towards fish and other vertebrates in the late 1990s, and a grassroots movement of fish genome studies is forming. Comprehensive genomic studies can unfold the mystery and guide toward the path of creating genetically modified fishes. There is considerable interest in genetically modified fish for the production of pharmaceuticals, innovative aquarium pets, and faster growing strains for human consumption. Initially, this was done through "shotgunning," which included injecting multiple copies of the target gene into the nucleus of the eggs, a procedure that had an extremely poor success rate. Subsequent technologies have become more complex, including viruses capable of inserting desired genes into chromosomes (Dunham, 2011).

In addition to this, to understand the behaviors of the fishes it is necessary to study the molecular ecology which encompasses the fields of molecular phylogenetics, population genetics and genomics. From the genetic point of view, the groups of interbreeding individuals that hardly exchange members with other populations are known as populations. To ascertain the differences between populations by studying their genotype frequencies, population genetics is used. Population genetic concepts are frequently used in fisheries management to determine the stocks that serve as harvest and management units. Populations are significant management units because if one population becomes low, it must recover on its own without replenishment from other populations. Phylogeography is concerned with the geographic distribution of genetic lineages, generally at the level of deep population structure e.g. species, and genera, whereas population structure is determined by variations in allele (or haplotype) frequencies (Avice *et al.*, 1987). The advancements in the field of processing of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) sequence data and later of nuclear DNA (nDNA) sequence data helped to identify the differences between alleles or haplotypes (Karl and Avice, 1993). The data from mtDNA can be used to predict the age of a certain population and to study the process of creating sister species through divergence of populations. Phylogeography is the field that connects the field of phylogenetics and population genetics. The availability of DNA sequence information has revolutionised the discipline of phylogenetics.

Researchers can sort out the links among fishes using models of DNA sequence evolution, from the oldest lineages to the most recent speciation events. Analysed genomic data can greatly enhance the fish conservation effort. To meet the goals of biodiversity conservation - “it is important to know the fundamental evolutionary lineages, both above and below the species level” (Helfman, 2009). From the evolutionary aspect, determining the ancient lineages through morphological examination cannot always suffice the need. These situations can easily be handled through molecular phylogenetic assessment.

By studying the novel genetic properties through genomic analysis can help in the maintenance of evolutionary potential (Frankham *et al.*, 2002). DNA data can help in species identification by using PCR technology. It is important to understand which species are entering the market and whether any restricted species are present. To identify a certain species in marketplaces, species specific diagnostic markers based on DNA data can be used (Shivji *et al.*, 2002). The use of DNA data to a range of wildlife management challenges is known as conservation genetics. The preservation of genetic variety, which helps organisms to fight disease and cope with changing environments, is a crucial objective in this study. Population genetic research can help to define boundaries between fishing stocks and management units within species. Molecular systematics can discover previously unknown species that could be harvested or depleted. Molecular forensics can reveal which species are entering the market and indicate how certain lawful harvests might be used to cover up the exploitation of endangered species.

Fishes are eukaryotic and their cellular genome is divided between the cytoplasmic organelles e.g. mitochondria, and nuclear genome. Similarities and differences can be observed in genome sequences in various ways such as, at whole genomes level that have undergone complete duplication, in larger scale blocks, at gene level, and at the level of individual bases. Regions encoding similarly related proteins are more likely to be found in closely related genomes. Alignments of homologous gene sequences reveal changes, typically in the form of single-site mutations, insertions, and deletions. Typically, there is a decent link between overall species divergence and divergence of particular gene and protein sequences (Lesk, 2017). To understand the fishes from the biological standpoint these cellular genomes can be sequenced and analyzed with the help of bioinformatics. Bioinformatics is a new science at the intersection of molecular biology and computer science. It refers to the use of computer databases and algorithms to examine proteins, genes, and the entire collection of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) that an organism consists of i.e. the genome. Making sense of the massive amounts of structural data and sequence data

generated by genome sequencing programs, proteomics, and other large scale molecular biology initiatives is a tedious task in biology. Bioinformatics tools include computer programs that aid in the discovery of fundamental mechanisms underlying biological issues including the structure and function of macromolecules, metabolic pathways, disease processes, and evolution.

The purpose of genomics is to determine and study an organism's whole DNA sequence, or genome. The genes encoded by DNA can be expressed as ribonucleic acid (RNA) transcripts, which are then translated into protein in many circumstances. Functional genomics is the study of gene and protein function using genomewide assays. It is now feasible to define an individual's genome, RNA collection (transcriptome), proteome, and even collections of metabolites and epigenetic modifications, as well as the catalog of creatures inhabiting the body, for humans and other animals. Comparative genomics is the study of genome sequences from different species or, in some circumstances, individuals within a species. Annotation of genomes, particularly for predicting genes and conserved regulatory elements can be aided by genome comparisons (Miller *et al.*, 2004). This kind of genomics study regarding fishes can contribute to the fields of fish biology, fish ecology, fish conservation, and fisheries management. Thus, fishes of great economic importance, demand this sort of study in order to overcome the newly emerging challenges in the fisheries sector. Proper implementation of the knowledge acquired from these studies can help in solving problems related to fish production.

Reference genome sequences and annotations (containing coding and non-coding regulatory elements), genome-wide polymorphism markers, efficient genotyping platforms, high-density and high-resolution linkage maps, and transcriptome resources including non-coding transcripts must be made available. Disease resistance, feed conversion efficiency, growth rate, processing yield, behavior, reproductive features, and tolerance to environmental stresses such as low dissolved oxygen, high or low water temperature, and salinity must all be understood at the genomic and genetic levels (Abdelrahman *et al.*, 2017).

1.1.1 The Genome

The total collection of DNA instructions present in a cell makes up the genome. The human genome is made up of 23 pairs of chromosomes while catla have 25 pairs that are found in the cell's nucleus and one tiny chromosome that is found in the mitochondria. Everything a person needs to grow and operate is encoded in their genome. All living things have DNA as their primary source of information. The term "genome" refers to an organism's whole DNA. While certain genomes, like those of viruses and bacteria, are exceedingly small, some

genomes, like those of some plants, can be nearly incomprehensibly enormous. Why there does not seem to be a consistent relationship between biological complexity and genome size is still somewhat perplexing. The human genome, for instance, has around 3 billion nucleotides. While 3 billion may seem like a lot, the genome of the uncommon Japanese flower known as *Paris japonica* is approximately 150 billion nucleotides large—50 times the size of the human genome. The cat genome contains roughly 1-1.5 billion nucleotides.

The DNA i.e. deoxyribonucleic acid molecule is a chemical formation of two complementary polynucleotide chains both coils around each other to form a double helix. The nucleotides chemically consist of deoxyribose sugar, phosphoric acid, and a nitrogenous base. There are four types of nitrogen containing nucleobases: adenine (A), thymine (T), cytosine(C), and guanine (G). There are weak hydrogen bonds between each pair of nitrogenous bases of the complementary strands. These A, T, C, Gs are alphabets for the language of life. The arrangement of the nucleotide in sequential order stores the information for biological functions.

1.1.1.1 The eukaryotic gene:

From a molecular point of view genes are the specific segments of DNA that become expressed and produce functional products such as RNA or polypeptides. An eukaryotic genome possesses a considerably large amount of region in DNA that does not code for anything known as the non coding regions. There are large non-coding regions between the genes which are known as Spacer sequences. There are non-coding regions within the gene i.e. introns, as a result the gene depicts a split structure. The coding regions of the gene are known as the exons (Figure 1). These non-coding regions within or between the eukaryotic genes contribute to the larger genome size. The eukaryotic genome shows a unique trait where the same gene is repeated several times and those repeated genes create a gene family. The members of the gene family can either be found in a clustered manner within a particular site of the DNA or in a dispersed manner in different chromosomes. These gene families mainly originated as a result of the duplication of their single ancestral gene. Sometime, some of the copies of that ancestral gene of the gene family lose their function due to mutation and deactivated genes become pseudogenes. The presence of gene families and pseudogene further enlarges the genome size in eukaryotes. The non coding regions present in the genome repeat themselves millions of times and these repetitive sequences make the genome size even larger.

Sometimes a particular gene can be found in different species that diverged due to speciation. The gene can play a similar role in different species. These genes

are called orthologous genes or orthologs. Orthologous genes found in different species come from a common ancestor.

Repetition of the same gene in a genome is known as gene duplication, a common phenomena in genomics through which gene functions become diversified and new genetic materials are generated. As it struggles for evolutionary preservation, every form of genetic change passes through three major stages: creation through mutation, fixation when it segregates in the population, and preservation when the fixed change is perpetuated. Gene duplications follow this trend with one major exception: the acquisition of genetic variations between the copies might modify the probability of both copies being preserved from the moment a new gene copy emerges (Innan and Kondrashov, 2010). Duplications of genes play an important role in the emergence of novel biological activities. Theoretical studies frequently assume that a duplication is selectively neutral in and of itself, and that after a duplication, one of the gene copies is released from purifying (stabilizing) selection, allowing for the development of a new function (Kondrashov *et al.*, 2002). New genes are frequently formed by whole or partial duplications of pre-existing genes. Long DNA segment duplications are continually created by infrequent mutations, can be fixed in a population by selection or random drift, and are prone to divergent evolution of the paralogous sequences following fixation, however gene conversion can hamper this process. Duplication-related mutations can develop via at least two mechanisms: uneven crossing-over and backward strand slippage during DNA replication (Kondrashov and Kondrashov, 2006). Gene duplication process generates a lot of copies of the same gene which increases the robustness. Robustness helps to tolerate the changes due to mutations in the genome and can eventually be helpful for evolutionary innovation (Wagner, 2008).

Figure 1: The structure of eukaryotic genes

1.1.1.2 The eukaryotic chromosome:

During mitotic cell division, the nucleus of the cell becomes severed into a number of bodies and at the end of the mitosis these bodies recreate the nucleus and these bodies are known as the chromosomes (Waldeyer, 1888; Darlington, 1932). Distinctive features of a eukaryotic chromosome is a centromere and two telomeres at each end. All the nucleotides of the entire genome of a eukaryote are distributed across a number of chromosomes. The double helical core DNA chemically binds with a histone octamer and coils around it, this structure is known as the nucleosome which is the fundamental packaging unit of a chromosome. The present in between the nucleosomes is known as Linker DNA. The nucleosomes later loops and coils and become packed into a 30 nm chromatin fiber. After further looping and coiling the 700 nm higher order chromatin is derived (Figure 2).

Sometimes a block of genes can be conserved in a similar order in the chromosomes of related species and this phenomenon is known as synteny. In case of closely related species there is a similarity between large syntenic blocks.

The genome is a complex structure where the chromosome is typically formed by the hierarchical folding of DNA helix into more intricate structures rather than a simple linear sequence of the DNA molecule (Woodcock, 2006) and the genome is found within the nucleus and the expression of the genes within the genome is dependent not only on the base sequence but also on its position (Egecioglu and Brickner, 2011). Genes control numerous nuclear processes which occur in special sites within the nucleus (Lamond and Spector, 2003). The most essential functions of the genome is the organization of transcription and DNA replication and repair Sites. It is well known that inactive genes are

mainly found in the condensed heterochromatin while the active ones are generally found in the decondensed euchromatin. The chromatin folding feature inhibits the regulatory factors to access the condensed chromatin domains thus acting as a regulatory mechanism (Dillon and Festenstein, 2002). The chromatin loops can affect the genome regulation by bringing the sequences to a close proximity or by segregating the sequences from each other; while the presence of a larger loop can drive the sequences away from the chromosome (Van Driel *et al.*, 2003). This type of placement of genes due to the looping of chromatin fiber regulates the function of those genes (Cremer *et al.*, 2003). The chromosome scaffold, which is made of proteins such as condensin, TOP2A, and KIF4, plays an important role in holding the chromatin into compact chromosomes. The highly compact form makes the individual chromosomes visible, and they form the classic four arm structure, a pair of sister chromatids attached to each other at the centromere.

Figure 2: The hierarchical folding model of chromosome condensation

1.1.1.3 Genome Sequencing:

In 1965, after the discovery of nucleic acid, first complete sequencing of yeast tRNA was achieved (Holley *et al.*, 1965). Afterwards several methods of DNA sequencing were developed such as for instance Sanger Sequencing (Sanger *et al.*, 1977), Next-Generation Sequencing, Cyclic Reversible Termination Sequencing, Pyrosequencing (Leamon and Rothberg, 2007), Sequencing by Ligation (Flicek and Birney, 2009), Genome Sequencing by Measuring pH (Merriman *et al.*, 2012), Single-Molecule Sequencing with Long Read Lengths (Eid *et al.*, 2009; Koren *et al.*, 2013), Self-Assembling DNA Nanoarrays (Drmanac *et al.*, 2010; Peters *et al.*, 2012).

The development of Next-generation sequencing (NGS) was groundbreaking in the arena of sequencing technology. The NGS technology developed by Illumina Technology involves four basic steps for the sequencing process, such as Preparation of Sample, Cluster Generation, Sequencing, and Data Analysis. In the first step, the nucleic acid samples e.g DNA or RNA are fragmented and adapters are added to the ends of the DNA fragments. Through reduced cycle amplification additional motifs such as the sequencing binding site, indices, and regions complementary to the flow cell oligonucleotide are introduced. In the step of clustering each fragment molecule is isothermally amplified. The flow cell is a glass slide with lanes where each lane is coated with a lawn which is composed of two types of oligonucleotides. The hybridization is enabled by the first of the two types of oligonucleotides on the surface. The adapters attached to the fragments bind with the flow cell oligonucleotides then a polymerase enzyme creates a complement of the hybridized fragment and makes it a double stranded molecule. The double stranded molecule is then denatured and the original template is washed away. Afterwards the strands are clonally amplified through bridge amplification. In the process of bridge amplification the strand folds over and the adapter region hybridizes to the second type of oligonucleotides on the flow cell. Polymerases generate the complementary strand forming a double stranded bridge which is later denatured and results in two single stranded copies of the molecule that are tethered to the flow cell. The process is then repeated over and over, and occurs simultaneously for millions of clusters resulting in clonal amplification of all the fragments. After bridge amplification, the reverse strands are cleaved and washed off, leaving only the forward strands. The 3' ends are blocked to prevent unwanted priming. Sequencing begins with the extension of the first sequencing primer to produce the first read. With each cycle fluorescently tagged nucleotides compete for addition to the growing chain. Only one nucleotide is incorporated based on the sequence of the template. After the addition of each nucleotide the clusters are excited by a light source and a characteristic fluorescent signal is emitted, this

proprietary process is called sequencing by synthesis. The number of cycles determines the length of the read. The emission wavelength, along with the signal intensity, determines the base call. For a given cluster, all identical strands are read simultaneously. Hundreds of millions of clusters are sequenced in a massively parallel process. After the completion of the first read, the read product is washed away. In this step, the index-1 read primer is introduced and hybridized to the template. The read is generated similar to the first read. After completion of the index read, the read product is washed off and the 3' ends of the template are deprotected. The template now folds over and binds the second oligonucleotide on the flow cell. Index-2 is read in the same manner as index-1. Polymerases extend to the second flow cell oligonucleotide forming a double stranded bridge of the DNA fragment. This double stranded DNA is then linearized and the 3' ends are blocked. The original forward strand is cleaved off and washed away leaving only the reverse strand. Read-2 begins with the introduction of the read-2 sequencing primer. As with read-1, the sequencing steps are repeated until the desired read length is achieved. The read-2 product is then washed away. This entire process generates millions of reads representing all the fragments. Sequences from pooled sample libraries are separated based on the unique indices introduced during the sample preparation. For each sample, reads with similar stretches of base calls are locally clustered. Forward and reverse reads are paired creating contiguous sequences. These contiguous sequences are aligned back to the reference genome for variant identification. The paired end information is used to resolve ambiguous alignments (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Genome sequencing by Illumina technology

1.1.1.4 Identification of genes in the genome:

The detection of genes must be unambiguous and errorless as it is the most influential and pivotal part of genome sequence analysis. For this task computer programs are used which can identify open reading frames (ORFs). ORFs are regions of DNA that starts with a start codon e.g. ATG, and ends with a stop codon and that makes the ORF a probable protein coding region. There can be two possible approaches for the gene identification process:

- Detection of regions similar to known coding regions from other organisms. As similar proteins can be found across different species, it helps in finding out a desired protein coding sequence matching with other organisms' data. These regions of interest can show amino acid

sequences identical to previously recorded proteins. These regions can also match Expressed Sequence Tags (ESTs) which are short cDNA sub-sequence used for identifying gene transcripts.

- Detection of genes from the properties of DNA itself. In this case computer programs are used for identifying exons and introns. The 5' and 3' exons are identified by finding out the TATA box and stop codon respectively. This method is more accurate in case of prokaryotes, due to the absence of introns, than eukaryotes.

1.1.2 The Proteome

All organisms need a set of proteins to maintain their biological functions and control the phenotype, the complete set of protein present in an organism's body is known as the proteome. Proteins are biomolecules which are the long chain of amino acids. DNA stores the necessary information in its base sequences and transcribes into a RNA molecule which finally translates into a protein molecule. The determination of genome sequence helps to reveal the amino-acid sequence for the expressed protein that surmises the proteome. There are several mechanisms that influences the genome-proteome relationship:

- The mechanism of alternative splicing (Figure 4), in eukaryotes, is able to generate a variety of products from a single gene. Through this mechanism, different mRNAs can be formed from the different combinations of all the exons present in the DNA. In the final processed (mature) mRNA, particular exon(s) can either be included or excluded, but the exons always appear in the order they are found in the genome.
- RNA editing is another mechanism, in both eukaryotes and prokaryotes, through which one or more proteins can be created by deleting, inserting or substituting a nucleotide of the RNA molecule. This process is rather infrequent than the previous one.

Figure 4: Alternative splicing

Eukaryotic genomes contain genes that code for proteins as well as non-coding RNAs, such as regulatory sections, pseudogenes, and a wide range of repetitive sequences. In eukaryotes, genes that produce proteins have exons that can be translated and introns that are spliced out before translation. The ability to omit one or more exons, known as variable splicing, complicates the link between gene base sequences and protein amino acid sequences. RNA editing frequently results in further variations between the DNA sequences in the genome and the amino acid sequences of proteins. The function of a protein is determined by its structure, protein structure depends on the amino-acid sequence, and the amino-acid sequence is determined by the DNA sequence.

1.1.3 Biological Databases

Subsequent to the development of next-generation sequencing (NGS) technology the magnitude of sequence data increased many folds. Massive technological advancements in the sectors of computational hardware and software made possible the analyses of datasets that are terabytes in size. To acquire, analyze, sort, and distribute these massive data, many databases or digital archives were built.

DNA sequence databases:

1. GenBank at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) in Bethesda (Benson *et al.*, 2012) representing over 4,50,000 species formally described (Sayers *et al.*, 2022).

2. the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)-Bank Nucleotide Sequence Database (EMBL-Bank), part of the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) at the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) in Hinxton, England (Brooksbank *et al.*, 2014; Pakseresht *et al.*, 2014)
3. DNA Database of Japan (DDBJ) at the National Institute of Genetics in Mishima (Ogasawara *et al.*, 2012; Kosuge *et al.*, 2014).

The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) coordinates all three databases, and they share and exchange data on a daily basis. GenBank, EMBLBank, and DDBJ are databases inside NCBI, EBI, and DDBJ, which include hundreds of other sites for studying sequence data. Members of the scientific community can contribute records directly to NCBI, EBI, and DDBJ sequence repositories.

Protein Databases:

These databases store the protein sequences. The NCBI collects the protein sequence data from the translated coding regions data of GenBank and also from other external databases such as UniProt (Schneider *et al.*, 2012), The Protein Information Resource (PIR), SWISS-PROT, Protein Research Foundation (PRF), and the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Rose *et al.*, 2012). Similar to the NCBI, the EBI also provides protein data from the databases mentioned above.

1.1.4 Quantitative traits

Complex characters or quantitative traits of an organism don't have a single gene working behind them rather than the effect of a group of genes interacting with each other. These traits are often controlled by the influences of both genetic and environmental and depicts a wide range of variation. These traits may include growth of an organism i.e. height and weight, metabolic activity due to enzyme kinetics, disease resistance and occurrence of several diseases, circadian rhythms etc. Quantitative traits are often polygenic and can be studied statistically by analyzing the quantitative trait loci (QTL) as well as conducting a genome-wide association study (GWAS) (Griffiths *et al.*, 2005).

Analysis of quantitative trait loci (QTL)

Certain regions of DNA belonging to different chromosomes, influencing a particular polygenic trait is known as the QTL (Complex Trait Consortium 2003). The genetic architecture and variations of a trait is dependent on the number of QTLs. A quantitative trait can be controlled by a few genes of large effects or by many genes of small effects. Once the genome annotation of an organism is done, the traits unrelated to the desired can easily be distinguished. There have been decades of research on quantitative traits (QT) as well as the

gene structural variants associated with the traits. The influence of millions of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) quantifiable across the whole genome on diverse phenotypes can be explored by using contemporary genomic tools and methodologies (Geldermann, 1975). QTLs are mainly derived from genome-wide association studies (GWAS) and the results of these studies can be found in public databases such as the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project (Lonsdale *et al.*, 2013) or Animal QTLdb (Hu *et al.*, 2019), e.g. human (Lappalainen *et al.*, 2013) as well as plants (Zhang *et al.*, 2017), fishes (Lv *et al.*, 2016), and cattle (Bouwman *et al.*, 2018). The primary target of QTL analysis is to analyze the impact of an SNP on a measurable feature i.e. trait. A QTL analysis can be performed by utilizing several resources such as, R-package e.g. GenomicTools, Machine learning methods based on regularization terms, and statistical methods.

In the twenty-first century, the fisheries and aquaculture industries are increasingly acknowledged for their crucial contribution to global food security and nutrition. To attain sustainable and equitable global fisheries and aquaculture, further development of this contribution demands the acceleration of revolutionary reforms in policy, management, innovation, and investment. Global aquatic animal production was expected to be 178 million tonnes in 2020, a little decline from the all-time high of 179 million tonnes in 2018. Capture fisheries provided 90 million tonnes (51%), while aquaculture produced 88 million tonnes (49 %). 63% (112 million tonnes) of total production was obtained from marine waters (70% from capture fisheries and 30% from aquaculture), and 37% (66 million tonnes) from inland water bodies (83% from aquaculture and 17% from capture fisheries)(FAO, 2022). The overall first sale value of worldwide production was anticipated to be USD 406 billion, with capture fisheries accounting for USD 141 billion and aquaculture accounting for USD 265 billion (FAO, 2022). From 1961 to 2019, global apparent consumption of aquatic foods climbed at a 3.0 % yearly pace, over double the rate of annual global population growth (1.6 %). From 9.0 kg (live weight equivalent) in 1961 to 20.5 kg in 2019, the per capita consumption of aquatic animal foods increased by around 1.4% each year. Preliminary 2020 numbers show a modest decrease to 20.2 kg. Aquaculture accounted for 56% of aquatic animal food output accessible for human consumption in the same year. Increased supply, changing customer tastes, technological developments, and wealth growth have all had a significant impact on per capita consumption of aquatic foods in recent years. Approximately 58.5 million people were employed as full-time, part-time, occasional, or unspecified workers in fisheries and aquaculture in 2020 where female employees consisted 21% of the total workforce. 35% of people worked

in aquaculture, while 65% worked in catch fisheries. Most of the fishers and fishermen were from Asian region which was 84% (FAO, 2022). In contrast with the global scenario, Bangladesh is rapidly growing her capture fishery industry (both marine and inland) with the help of increasing fishing fleet, as a result, in 2020, there were a total number of 33097 motorized fishing vessels and among them 205 were large vessels (>24m), and a total number of 34810 non-motorized fishing boats (FAO, 2022). *C. catla* is one of the major aquaculture species worldwide. In 2020, this Indian Major Carp (*C. catla*) contributed 7.2% (3540.3 thousand tonnes) of the world production among the major aquaculture species, which was in 5th position (FAO, 2022). In Bangladesh, in 2019-20, the fisheries industry provided 3.52% of national GDP which was more than one-fourth of agricultural GDP (26.37%). More than 12% of (almost 170 million) people in Bangladesh rely on fisheries and aquaculture-related industries for a living, both full-time and part-time (DoF, 2020). In Fiscal Year (FY) 2019-20 production of *C. catla* in Bangladesh was 2,58,497 Metric Tons, which was 6.75% of total annual fish from inland waterbodies and that put the catla in 6th position among other species (DoF, 2020).

1.2 Locations relevant to the study

Bangladesh is renowned for its rivers, which have one of the greatest networks in the world, with around 700 rivers and tributaries totaling approximately 24,140 kilometers in length. They are composed of tiny hilly streams, meandering seasonal creeks, murky canals, and some genuinely gorgeous rivers, as well as their tributaries and distributaries. The only two internal rivers that begin and end within Bangladesh are the Sangu and Halda. The river Halda harbors extremely valuable brood fishes of catla and supports the natural spawning of them thus helps in maintaining wild gene pool of the species. Recently the whole genome sequence of catla from Halda River was revealed through a joint venture of Halda River Research Laboratory (HRRL) and Chattogram Veterinary and Animal Sciences University (CVASU). In this study, sequenced and assembled data of catla from Halda River was used for chromosome orientation and comparative genome analysis.

1.2.1 Halda River

The Halda River is a prominent river in Bangladesh's south-east area. It is named after Halda Chora, which is located in Ramgarh Upazila, Khagrachari District, Bangladesh. It runs through Fatikchhari, Hathazari, Raozan, and Chittagong Chandgaon Thana before emptying into the Karnaphuli River (Figure 5). The Dhurung River, a 98 kilometer long tributary, meets the river around 48.25 kilometers downstream near Sundarpore. The river can be navigated by large

boats 29 kilometers into it (up to Nazirhat) and by small boats 16-24 kilometers beyond (up to Narayanhat). Halda is an indigenous river of Bangladesh that originates and ends within the country (Figure 6). Geographic coordinate: 22°33'34.7"N 91°50'41.8"E. The river originates from Hasuk para of Choto Belchori (Ward no 7), situated in Ramgarh Upazila. The width of the river varies from 75 to 210 m in width at different points (Tsai *et al.*, 1981).

1.2.2 Halda River Research Laboratory (HRRL)

HRRL (22°46'77 39 N, 91 77 80 799"E) is a specialist research laboratory of the University of Chittagong, Hathazari that monitors river health by concentrating on environmental and river ecosystem physical, chemical, and biological aspects. This laboratory maintains the Halda River's resources, history, culture, and traditions while also contributing to the development of the Halda River's indigenous technique of IMC's egg harvesting. The lab is dedicated to develop Halda River indigenous technology, monitor the Halda River health regularly, establish a Center of Excellence for research on the rivers in Bangladesh and create mass awareness to protect the river's ecology.

The country's first single-river research laboratory "Halda River Research Laboratory" was established in the Biological Faculty of Chittagong University with the assistance of IDF and PKSf. It is the only single river research laboratory of Bangladesh.

All types of research on Halda River can be done from this laboratory. Not only CU, but other universities of the country can also conduct and register research activities here.

The research center has a lab with sophisticated equipment. All necessary equipment of river research along with water quality and location specification has been added here. If everything is available from one place, then not only the Halda, It will be easy for governments and researchers to decide on all the rivers of the country from one place. In the case of river research, it will be a milestone in future.

1.2.3 Chattogram Veterinary and Animal Sciences University (CVASU)

CVASU (22°36 27.629" N, 91°80'21.4177E) is the most specialized university for veterinary study which is situated at Khulshi, Chattogram. It has campuses also in Hathazari, Chattogram, Purbachal, Dhaka and Dariyanagar, Cox's Bazar. A partial part of the analyses were done here.

Figure 5: Location of Halda River

Figure 6: Map of Halda River

1.3 Halda River and its ecology

A river is viewed by an earth scientist as a link in the hydrologic cycle; a site of erosion, transportation, and deposition of dissolved, suspended, and tractively carried geologic materials; and a complete open physical system hydrodynamically balancing and distributing energy and work across the earth's land areas. Rivers are also considered as the arteries of the catchment ecosystem. The river Halda naturally inhabits four major carps e.g. *Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla*, *Cirrhinus cirrhosus* and *Labeo calbasu* (Tsai *et al.*, 1981) as well as the Gangetic River Dolphin (*Platanista gangetica*) (Smith *et al.*, 2001). The most noticeable element is the process for harvesting fertilized IMCS eggs directly from the river. The river provides drinking and irrigation water, as well as a fishing area and a mode of water transportation (Kabir *et al.*, 2015). Hundreds of people rely completely on the river's natural resources for a living. Depending on the river, the riverine area has evolved its own culture and lifestyle (Kabir *et al.*, 2013). It is regarded as a lifeline for the city of Chantogram since Halda river meets the city's water needs. Different man-made and natural disasters such as ox-bow cutting, massive quarrying of sands from the river bed illegally by a section of unscrupulous traders, pollution of the river by industrial waste, unplanned construction of a good number of sluice gates by the locals for irrigation purposes, indiscriminate catching and killing of the brood fishes, and climate change in the river have all posed a serious threat to the Halda's biodiversity. Because of these risk concerns, the river that was once a refuge for brood fishes to release their eggs has now become rather risky, resulting in a severe drop in the availability of eggs and fish-fries of native species as fewer brood fishes have been here in recent years to release eggs.

1.4 Halda River Fisheries and its Economic aspects

Bangladesh is an outflow pathway for the complicated Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna river system, as well as a significant supplier of fishery resources. Bangladesh's inland water has 264 different species of fish (Rahman, 2005). In addition to 475 marine fish species, 65 economically significant fish species have been reported (Hossain, 1970), and 12 exotic fish culturable species have been introduced in Bangladesh (DoF, 2020). The enormous inland water system, which covers 4.57 million hectares and includes a 3.86 million hectare floodplain, riverine, and estuarine system, offers a great habitat for this taxonomically diversified fish fauna. The Ganges-Brahmaputra river systems are physically separated from the River Halda, which is an ecosystem with a variety of species. This river contains a diverse assortment of fish species from the floodplain, river, estuary, and ocean, with a few species having a considerable

predominance over others. A total of 93 species of finfish and shellfish was identified from the river (Azadi and Alam, 2013). The diversity of finfish found in the river was astounding, totaling 83 species under 13 orders, 35 families, and 69 genera. Three species of exotic fish were also recorded. A considerable amount of shellfish species was identified from the river, and the total number of shellfish species was 10 belonging to 01 order, 3 families, and 3 genera. The identified finfish families were Adrianichthyidae, Anabantidae, Anguillidae, Aplocheilidae, Belonidae, Cichlidae, Clariidae, Cynoglossidae, Hemiramphidae, Heteropneustidae, Notopteridae, Ophichthidae, Opistognathidae, Pangasiidae, Platycephalidae, Polynemidae, Scatophagidae, Sillaginidae, Soleidae, Syngnathidae representing only a single species each. Moringuidae, Mugilidae, Osphronemidae, Sciaenidae, Siluridae each contained 2 species. Ambassidae, Channidae, Mastacembelidae had 3 species each. 4 species identified from both Clupeidae, Bagridae families. Family Schilbeidae, Gobiidae, and Cyprinidae contained 5, 11, and 20 species respectively. Nine prawn species from the families Palaemonidae and Penaeidae; and one crab species from the family Portunidae was identified (Azadi and Alam, 2013). Halda possesses an important value in the fisheries sector of the country. It is the only river in the country where naturally spawned eggs of IMCs are collected and hatched in earthen pits built in the river bank by the local fishermen and egg collectors. This unique feature made the river a national heritage, and as a result, the Government of Bangladesh declared this river as "Bangabondhu Fishery Heritage" back in 2020. Realizing the ecological importance of the river, several government and non-government organizations have come forward to help the fishermen regarding hatching of collected eggs by constructing modern hatcheries and giving required technological support to them. Halda, most importantly, supports the local fishing community and the community dependent on agriculture. Halda contributes to the economy and supports the local fishermen as they collect prawn, post larvae of prawn, fish, and fish fry from it (Kabir *et al.*, 2013). Halda serves as a waterway for transporting both passengers and merchant products and there were at least 29 boat stations (Kabir *et al.*, 2013). The river also supports agriculture in the area by supplying irrigation water. It was estimated that, annually Halda can provide a net worth of USD 20.5 million (Kabir *et al.*, 2013) from all sorts of resources within its vicinity. In 2020, 394 Kg of spawn was collected from Halda River and the sale rate of the spawn was 4300 Tk/Kg (DoF, 2020).

1.5 Description of *C. catla*

1.5.1 Taxonomy

Catla catla (Hamilton, 1822) belongs to the superclass of ray-finned fishes, i.e. Actinopterygii. Around 400 million years ago (mya) actinopterygians first appeared and later gave rise to two groups of fish, which are Cladistia (bichirs and reedfishes) and Actinopteri. The origin of Actinopteri dates back to the Permian period, and this group includes all the extant Actinopterygians, except the Polypteridae (bichirs). Later on, the actinopteri became branched into two groups, which are the Neopterygii (bowfin, gars, and teleosts) and the Chondrostei (sturgeons and paddlefish) (Near *et al.*, 2012). Neopterygians first appeared around 360 mya; they developed a more modified skull structure and better control over the movements of both anal and dorsal fins (Friedman and Sallan, 2012). Neopterygians are further subdivided into two infraclasses: Holostei (gars, alligator gars, and bowfins) and Teleostei. Teleostei became evident around 310 mya and is by far the largest infraclass (containing more than 26000 species) under the class Actinopterygii. The order Cypriniformes (carps, minnows, and loaches) belongs to the group Teleostei (Benton, 2014). Cyprinidae and other related species' evolutionary positions and phylogenetic relationships were examined using phylogenetic analysis. By using complete mitochondrial genome sequences, it was observed that, catla was clustered with other carp species belonging to the family Cyprinidae, and it was also noticed that catla was forming a sister clade with *Cirrhinus cirrhosus* and a clade with *Labeo rohita* (Bej *et al.*, 2012).

Common name: Catla (English name), **Bangla name:** Catla, Katal, Katol

Systematic position:

Kingdom	Animalia
Subkingdom	Bilateria
Infrakingdom	Deuterostomia
Phylum	Chordata
Subphylum	Vertebrata
Infraphylum	Gnathostomata
Superclass	Actinopterygii
Class	Teleostei
Superorder	Ostariophysi
Order	Cypriniformes
Superfamily	Cyprinoidea
Family	Cyprinidae

Genus	<i>Catla</i>
Species	<i>Catla catla</i> (Hamilton, 1822)

Synonyms:

Cyprinus catla Hamilton, 1822

Gebelion catla Hamilton, 1822

Cyprinus abraminoides Sykes, 1841

Catla buchanani Day, 1878

Catla catla Jhingran, 1966

1.5.2 Morphological Features

The catla has a compressed body which is comparatively short with a broad head. The body is deep, mostly 2.5–3 times deeper in standard depth (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991). Body color is grayish on the back and flanks but silver-white at the abdomen. The mouth is large and wide, upturned (Bhowmick *et al.*, 1987), and has a prominently protruding lower jaw (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991). The upper lip is thin and prominent, covered by the skin of the snout. The lower lip is moderately thick, broad, and a continuous post labial groove is present. Lower possesses movable articulation at its symphysis. Long and fine gill rakers are present on the gill arch. Three rows of pharyngeal teeth are present in the pharyngeal arch of the throat following the 5.3.2/2.3.5 pattern. The dorsal profile is more convex than that of the abdomen. Lateral line complete with 40–43 scales. Pectoral fins are long and extend to the pelvic fins; scales are conspicuously large (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991). The scale number on the lateral line series is 40 to 43. Scale numbers mentioned by other writers are as follows: 40–43 scales above the lateral line series (Rahman, ud.); 40–45 scales above the lateral series (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991). Dorsal rays are 17 in number and soft. 7-8 soft anal rays are present with no anal spine. Pectoral fins are long, extending to the pelvic fins. Fins are dusky in color. The Gill opening is circular, and the body is deepest at the origin of the dorsal.

Fin formula:

D. 3-4/14-16, P1. 1/20, P2. 1/8, A. 3/5

D. 2/15-16, P1. 18-20, P2. 9, A. 3/5 (Rahman, 2005)

D. 3-4/14-16, P1. 21, P2. 9, A. 3/5 (Bhuiyan, 1964)

1.5.3 Habitat and Distribution

Catla catla is extensively spread across Bangladesh's inland freshwater habitats, while its abundance is modest. Despite its continuous decline due to previous and present challenges, the drop in population abundance appears to be less than 20% during the last 6-7 years (Ahmed *et al.*, 2003). Captive breeding of the species is common, and the fish is farmed extensively in practically every section of the country. Catla is native to Bangladesh (Rahman, 1989), India (Froese and Pauly, 2002), Myanmar (Froese and Pauly, 2002), Nepal (Shrestha, 1994), and Pakistan (Akhtar, 1991). During the 1960s and later this species was introduced to several other countries outside their natural habitat such as Mauritius, Zimbabwe, Bhutan, Cambodia, China, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, Vietnam, and Russia (Seebens *et al.*, 2017) (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Distribution of *C. catla*

1.5.4 Feeding Habit

C. catla is a planktivorous carp species that feeds mostly on zooplankton. Adults generally feed in surface and mid-waters. The fry are also planktivorous, feeding mainly on zooplankton such as cladocerans and rotifers. The digestive system is quite short and straight in the beginning; folding of the digestive system begins on day 9 after hatching, and coiling is observable after 19 days. The digestive system consists of the throat, oesophagus, intestine, and vent; there is no stomach.

1.5.5 Breeding Biology

Catla matures in its second year, after gaining an average weight of 2 Kg, when it embarks on a spawning journey during the monsoon season to the upper reaches of rivers, where males and females gather and breed in shallow marginal

regions. The spawning season corresponds with the south-west monsoon in north-eastern India and Bangladesh, which lasts from May to August, and from June to September in north India and Pakistan. Its fecundity ranges from 100 000 to 200 000/kg Body Weight (BW), depending on the length and weight of the fish. The resulting seeds are carried downstream by water flow and collected by seed collectors. Initially demersal, the eggs progressively become buoyant. Early-stage larvae are phototactic and persist in surface and subsurface waters. Three days after hatching, the larvae begin to eat, but their yolk sacs remain. The number of gill rakers and gill filaments grows as they grow, aiding them in straining ingested food particles. The ox-bow bends in Halda serve as the main spawning grounds (Tsai *et al.*, 1981). When water rushes into the curvatures, it pours into the deep pools and against the curvatures' outer bank, generating turbulence and upwelling currents along the inner bank as well as downstream from the pools. There was also a counter-flow stream running along the inner bank of the curvatures. These special spawning sites are locally known as the “Kum”. In order to facilitate a successful spawning and to stimulate the brood fishes properly and simultaneously, several environmental stimuli and influential factors such as thunderstorms and rainfall, tidal cycle and water level, air and water temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH, turbidity and current velocity, conductivity must be at optimum level in the river. Natural breeding of catla does not occur within ponds since a riverine habitat is necessary, even when the species reaches maturity; hence, hormone induction is required. Catla is one of the most difficult among the Indian major carps to breed because it demands exact environmental conditions for spawning.

1.5.6 Economic Importance

The main producer countries of Catla are India, Nepal, Myanmar, Laos, and Bangladesh (Figure 8). In Bangladesh, after Rui, Catla is the second most popular species in IMCs polyculture system in Bangladesh. Catla contributes a large share in the country's both inland culture and capture fisheries. This species helps significantly in the effort for food security by providing safer and quality animal protein to meet up the ever growing need for protein, besides people's livelihood are also dependent on the culture, transportation, and marketing of the species. Catla can provide a great deal of nutrition to the country's population as it contains Protein – 19gm/100gm, Calcium – 530mg/100gm, and 22.7% of its fat contents contains omega-3 fatty acid (Mohanty *et al.*, 2016) which is highest among indigenous major carps. Catla can be found in a wide variety of water bodies inside the country such as rivers, beels, lakes, flood plains, baor, ponds etc. In 2019-20 FY, the production of catla from different inland water bodies was 2,58,497 metric ton (DoF, 2020), which

was 17,939 metric ton more than the previous year's production of 2,40,558 metric ton (DoF, 2019) and that indicates, this species with proper wild stock management and proper supervision of culture system, can have a great impact in facing the future challenges regarding national food security and economy.

Figure 8: Main producer countries of *C. catla*

1.6 Aims and Objectives

Catla is a species of great importance in the fisheries sector and countries economy. Catla from Halda river plays an even more important role by producing naturally spawned eggs which are eventually collected and hatched to fish fry and to be sold in the fish fry market. This breeding population of Catla from Halda River must be prioritized and their genetic features must be identified for the quality assessment of hatchery stocks and for conservation efforts in future and in order to achieve that, this study aims-

1. To achieve the chromosome level genome assembly of *C. catla*
2. To determine the genetic variation of *C. catla* through functional genomics.
3. To explore unique genetic features of Halda fishes and to determine candidate genes for several important traits of *C. catla*.

Chapter 02

Review of Literatures

2.1 Chromosome level assembly

Arick *et al.* (2022) assembled a high quality *de novo* genome of *Labeo rohita* by engaging several next-generation sequencing technologies where they revealed a genome of 946 Mb consisting of 25 chromosomes with 2,844 unplaced scaffolds. For the assembly, first of all, adapter contents, shorter reads (<85 bp), and low quality bases were removed by using Trimmomatic v0.32 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) and shorter sequences (<1000 bases) and control lambda-phage were filtered by employing the nanopack tool suite v1.0.1 (De Coster *et al.*, 2018). Contigs were assembled from filtered nanopore data with the help of wtdbg2 v2.4 (Ruan and Li, 2020) and were polished by using racon v1.4.0 (Vaser *et al.*, 2017) and minimap2 v2.17 (Li, 2018). The contigs were refined further using Illumina paired end read data using pilon v1.23 (Walker *et al.*, 2014) with bwa v0.7.10 (Li, 2013) mapping the Illumina paired reads. Scaffolding of the resulting contigs was done by using SALSA v2.3 (Ghurye *et al.*, 2019) and Bionano Solve. Larger scaffolds (>10Mb) were connected and orientated using RagTag v1.1.1 (Alonge *et al.*, 2021) based on a comparable genome (*Onychostoma macrolepis* genome) (Sun *et al.*, 2020). Repeat database (species-specific) was constructed and masked by employing RepeatMasker v4.1.1 (Smit *et al.*, 2013) and RepeatModeler v2.0.1 (Flynn *et al.*, 2020). Gene prediction was done with the help of Maker2 v2.31.10 (Holt and Yandell, 2011) and genes that span wide gaps or are entirely enclosed within another gene on the other strand were eliminated.

Xie *et al.* (2022), performed a chromosome level assembly of *Cephalopholis sonnerati* (Tomato Hind) from the sequence data derived from PacBio sequencing and Hi-C technologies and found a genome of 1043.66 Mb and the contig N50 length was 2.49 Mb. A total of 795 contigs oriented into 24 chromosomes with 97.2% of complete BUSCOs were found. 94.26% of the predicted genes were functionally annotated from a total number of 21,130 predicted genes. Mecat2 (Xiao *et al.*, 2017) was used for the draft genome assembly and then gcpp 1.9.0 was used for the polishing of the initial assembly in order to correct the errors of the primary assembly. Genome completeness was evaluated by using BUSCO v3.0 (Simão *et al.*, 2015) with actinoperygii_odb9. For the construction of pseudochromosomes Hi-C sequencing libraries were mapped against the polished genome with the help of bwa 0.7.17 (Li, 2013) by creating Hi-C associated scaffolds. Contigs were clustered and oriented by using Lachesis (Burton *et al.*, 2013) and the visual

error correction of the assembly was done by using Juicer v1.6.2 (Durand *et al.*, 2016). Identification of the repeat contents was completed by two approaches such as, the *de novo* and homology based method. RepeatMasker 4.0.9 (Chen, 2004) was used for the homology based identification of repeat contents while *de novo* identification of repeat contents was done by using RepeatModeler (Flynn *et al.*, 2020) which was the combination of two programs e.g. RECON v1.08 (Bao and Eddy 2002) and RepeatScout v1.0.5 (Price *et al.*, 2005). Identification of long terminal repeats and tandem repeats were done with the help of LTR_FINDER v1.0.7 (Xu and Wang, 2007) and Tandem Repeat Finder (TRF) package (Benson, 1999). Different library files were merged with the help of RepeatMasker to obtain the final repeat contents. Gene prediction was done by following three methods e.g. homology-based, *de novo*, and transcriptome sequencing based. Homology-based prediction of genes was done by using exonerate v2.2.0. *De novo* gene prediction was done with the help of Genscan (Burge and Karlin, 1997) and Augustus v3.3.1 (Stanke *et al.*, 2004). Transcriptome sequencing based gene prediction was done by using GMAP v4 (Wu and Watanabe, 2005). Results from the three prediction methods were unified by using Maker v3.0 (Cantarel *et al.*, 2008) to obtain the final prediction of gene models.

Ding *et al.* (2021), performed a chromosome level genome assembly of *Siniperca chuatsi* (mandarin fish) and found 92.8% of the scaffolds belonging to 24 chromosomes from an assembled genome size of 758.78 Mb, where the scaffold and contig N50 values were 2.64 Mb and 46.11 Kb, respectively. From the assembly 19904 protein-coding genes were identified and 95.75% of those genes were functionally annotated. Original scaffolds and contigs were generated by SOAPdenovo2 (v2.04); GapCloser (v1.12) was utilized to fill the gaps of intra-scaffolds; and genome integrity was assessed by BUSCO (Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs; v1.22). *De novo* repeat library was generated by using RepeatModeler (v1.0.8) and LTR_FINDER (v1.0.6) with default parameters, and repeat regions in the built repeat library were identified through RepeatMasker. *De novo* gene prediction was done by employing GENSCAN (v1.0) and AUGUSTUS (v3.2.1); homology based gene prediction was done by aligning homologous proteins of several other species with the help of tblastn (v2.2.26). All the potential gene structures from other alignments were defined through executing GeneWise (v2.4.1) and Solar (v0.9.6). Transcriptome based gene prediction was done by using tophat (v2.0.13) and structures of those genes were predicted by cufflinks (v2.1.1). GLEAN (v1.0) was used to merge the datasets discussed above to generate a complete and uniform gene set. These predicted genes were annotated by

aligning them against Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG), gene ontology (GO), and Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL with the help of BLASTP. InterProScan (v5.16–55.0) was used for the identification of domains and functional motifs through PRINTS, Pfam, SMART, and ProDom databases. Predicted genes were clustered into families by executing OrthoMCL (v1.4) then MUSCLE (v3.8.31) was employed to accomplish multiple sequence alignment and a phylogenetic tree was constructed by using PhyML (v3.0). JoinMap4.1 was used for assigning linkage groups to reconstruct the linkage map and SNPs from the linkage map helped to generate the chromosome assembly. Synteny analysis was performed against a reference genome from NCBI and lastz was employed to execute genome-wide alignments.

Huang *et al.* (2021) performed a chromosome level assembly of *Scatophagus argus* (Spotted Scat) and oriented the 572.42 Mb genome sequence into 24 chromosomes ranging from 12.57-30.38 Mb with a scaffold N50 of 24.67 Mb. From 24,256 predicted genes 23,358 genes (96.30%) were functionally annotated. Primary genome was done by WTDBG v1.0 while CANU v1.5 (Koren *et al.*, 2017) was used for the correction of SMRT bell library subreads. Corrected contigs from primary assembly and were used for chromosomal-level genome assembly with the help of Lachesis (Burton *et al.*, 2013). Genome assemblies were assessed against eukaryotic genes and Actinopterygii genes by using CEGMA v2.5 (Parra *et al.*, 2007) and BUSCO v2.0 (Simão *et al.*, 2015) respectively. Construction of a *de novo* repeat library was done with the help of Piler-DF v2.4 (Edgar and Myers, 2005), Repeatscout v1.0.5 (Price *et al.*, 2005), and LTRfinder v1.05 (Xu and Wang, 2007). Homolog-based gene prediction was done by Gemoma v1.3.1 (Keilwagen *et al.*, 2016), RNA-seq based gene prediction was done by Hisat v2.0.4 (Kim *et al.*, 2015), and *ab initio* based gene prediction was done by Augustus v2.4 (Stanke and Waack, 2003) and Genscan v3.1 (Burge and Karlin, 1997). The chromosomal-level genome included 99.19% of the 248 essential eukaryotic genes and 96.97% of the 4,584 core genes in the Actinopterygii database, according to the Core Eukaryotic Genes Mapping Approach (CEGMA) and Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs (BUSCO) analyses.

Gao *et al.* (2021a) achieved a chromosome level assembly of *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* (Striped catfish) by arranging the 731.7 Mb genome sequence into 30 pseudochromosomes with a contig N50 of 3.5 Mb and a scaffold N50 of 29.50 Mb. Number of predicted protein coding genes were 18,895 and 36.9% repeat sequences. Low quality short reads from the sequencing data were filtered by using SOAPnuke v1.0 (Chen *et al.*, 2018) and long sequencing reads were calibrated by applying LoRDEC (Salmela and Rivals, 2014) before the genome

assembly. Corrected long reads were assembled into contigs by minimap2 (Li, 2018) and genome polishing was done in two steps with the help of pilon (Walker *et al.*, 2014) and Racon v1.3.1 (Vaser *et al.*, 2017). Clean reads from Hi-C data were mapped to the assembled draft genome by using Bowtie2 (Langdon, 2015) and later these reads were clustered, ordered and oriented with the help of Juicer (Durand *et al.*, 2016) and 3d-dna (Dudchenko *et al.*, 2017) and then the assembled genome was affixed to 30 chromosomes.

Zhao *et al.* (2021), performed a chromosome level assembly of *Argyrosomus japonicus* from the sequence data derived from PacBio sequencing and Hi-C technologies and found an assembled genome of 637.7 Mb and the contig N50 length was 18.4 Mb. A total of 282 contigs oriented into 24 chromosomes with 97% of complete BUSCOs were found and the amount of repeat contents was 217.2 Mb (34.06%). A total of 22,938 genes (97.34%) were functionally annotated from a total number of 23,730 predicted genes. The genome assembly was done by analyzing PacBio long reads with the help of CANU (Koren *et al.*, 2017) after determining the k-mer values of heterozygosity, size, and repeat content by using jellyfish (Marçais and Kingsford, 2011). Polishing and correction in the assembly were done by employing the Quiver algorithm (Chin *et al.*, 2013) using PacBio long reads and pilon (Walker *et al.*, 2014) with the Illumina clean reads respectively. Chromosome level scaffolding was done by mapping of cleaned Hi-C reads to the assembled genome with the help of BWA (Li and Durbin, 2009). Assembled contigs were clustered, ordered, and oriented by using Lachesis (Burton *et al.*, 2013). The quality of the assembly was assessed by checking the accuracy and completeness via sequenced read mapping and benchmarking universal single-copy ortholog (BUSCO) analysis (Seppey *et al.*, 2019). Tandem repeats and repeat sequences were identified with the help of Tandem Repeat Finder (TRF) package (Benson, 1999) and RepeatModeler (Flynn *et al.*, 2020) respectively. Repeat elements and transposable elements (TE) proteins were annotated by utilizing the rebase library with the help of RepeatMasker and RepeatProteinMasker respectively (Bao *et al.*, 2015). Gene prediction was done by following three methods e.g. homology-based, de novo, and transcriptome sequencing based. Homology-based prediction of genes was done by aligning protein sequences from several other species against the assembled genome of *A. japonicus* with the help of TblastN (Gertz *et al.*, 2006). De novo gene prediction was done with the help of Genscan (Burge and Karlin, 1997) and Augustus (Stanke *et al.*, 2008). Transcriptome sequencing based gene prediction was done by aligning the transcriptome sequence reads against the genome with the help of the TopHat package (Trapnell *et al.*, 2009) and Cufflinks (Ghosh and Chan, 2016) was used

for the prediction of gene structure. Results from the three prediction methods were unified by using Maker (Cantarel *et al.*, 2008) to obtain the final prediction of gene models.

Sun *et al.*, (2020) performed a chromosome level assembly of *Onychostoma macrolepis* from the sequence data gathered from the combination of Nanopore long-read sequencing with physical maps produced using Bionano and Hi-C technology and found a primary assembled genome of 883.2 Mb and the contig N50 length was 11.2 Mb. Bionano optical mapping was used for contig correction and 969 corrected contigs were obtained and later aggregated into 853 scaffolds amounting 886.5 Mb assembly where the scaffold N50 was 16.5 Mb. The Hi-C data produced a total of 526 scaffolds from 881.3 Mb (99.4%) of the genome and finally the scaffolds were anchored and oriented in 25 chromosomes ranging in size from 25.27 to 56.49 Mb. A total of 23,991 genes (96.85%) were functionally annotated from a total number of 24,770 predicted genes. Scaffold construction was done by using WTDBG (Ruan and Li, 2020) and the accuracy of the assembly was improved by using BWA v0.7.10 (Li, 2013) and Pilon (Walker *et al.*, 2014). For the chromosome assembly, firstly, quality control and filtration of Hi-c data were done by using Hi-C Pro v2.8.0 (Burton *et al.*, 2013) and fastp v0.12.6 (Chen *et al.*, 2018) respectively, then bowtie2 v2.3.2 (Langmead and Salzberg, 2012) was used for the unique mapping of clean paired-end reads to the draft assembly. Finally, the contigs were clustered, ordered, and oriented by using Lachesis (Burton *et al.*, 2013) following an agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithm.

2.2 Quantitative trait loci (QTL) analysis

Robledo *et al.*, (2016) identified the single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within the growth related candidate genes of *Scophthalmus maximus* (Turbot) through a combined approach of QTL, genome, and transcriptome analyses. On the basis of QTL co-localization and trait functions 45 SNPs were selected and out of those 45 SNPs 43 were validated in a wild population. Necessary genes associated with growth were sorted out on the basis of gene ontology by using Blast2GO (Conesa *et al.*, 2005) and previous reports. Corresponding sequences were gathered from Ensembl release 75 (Flicek *et al.*, 2014) from species closely related to turbot. Orthologous sequences of turbot were obtained from the earlier retrieved sequences with the help of local BLAST (Xu *et al.*, 2014) and later these obtained sequences were confirmed by blasting them against NCBI protein databases and their position in the turbot genome were also obtained. Co-localization of growth related genes in the genetic map were checked by utilizing local BLAST (Altschul *et al.*, 1997) against the growth QTL markers. As there

weren't any associated markers for the growth related QTLs, co-localization of the genes was predicted on the basis of closest markers to the QTL position in the genetic map. Pileup function in SAMtools utilities v.0.1.19 (Li *et al.*, 2009) was used for the localization of SNPs within the aligned reads.

Yu *et al.*, (2016) mapped (genome wide) the QTLs related to growth in *Epinephelus coioides* (Orange-Spotted Grouper). A genetic linkage map was constructed involving 3029 SNPs from a total of 264,072 raw identified SNPs. There were a total of 24 linkage groups covering a total 1231.98 cM genetic distance and a total of 27 QTLs associated with growth were also identified. The QTLs were mapped and calculated by composite interval mapping (CIM) (Silva *et al.*, 2012) method with the help of WinQTLCart2.5 software (Wang S., Basten C.J. and Zeng Z.-B., Raleigh N.C., USA). Scaffolds of desired QTL regions were identified to obtain the growth related QTLs and the genes were also mapped based on their positions on the scaffolds and later the homologous genes were sorted out from the annotation file.

Wringe *et al.*, (2010) analyzed the QTLs associated with growth in both wild and domestic *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (rainbow trout). QTLs related to body weight and condition factors were detected and co-localized within the genome. Linkage groups were identified by using LINKMFEX a visual basic program. Relations between allelic segregation and trait variations were analyzed at marker loci with the help of MultiQTL v2.5.

Ma *et al.*, (2021) identified and analyzed QTLs related to upper temperature tolerance in *Scophthalmus maximus* (Turbot). A genetic linkage map of 22 linkage groups were constructed from a total of 190 simple sequence repeats (SSR) and 8,123 SNPs and the map expanded 3,648.29 cM with an average interval of 0.44 cM in the genome. 2 linked SSRs and 206 SNP loci from 13 different QTLs showed important QTL effects. From 129 QTL markers 8 SNP loci showed significant correlation with upper temperature tolerance trait. A total of 1363 genes and 26 QTL markers were found to be effective in thermal tolerance. Calculation of scores between markers and construction genetic map were done by using modified logarithm of odds (MLOD) and HighMap (Liu *et al.*, 2014) respectively. A high density genetic map constructed from the ordered and oriented by using ALLMAPS (Tang *et al.*, 2015). QTLs related to upper temperature tolerance was analyzed by using MapQTL 5.0 and interval QTL mapping model was used for the calculation of genotypic information coefficient and percentage of the phenotypic variance, and detection of QTL regions.

Houston *et al.*, (2007) determined the major QTLs in *Salmo salar* (Atlantic Salmon) related to the infectious pancreatic necrosis i.e. a viral disease

resistance. Linkage groups having significant effects on the disease were detected by analyzing the QTLs using a sire-based method with the help of 2-3 microsatellite markers per linkage group. Detected QTLs, later, confirmed and positioned by using a dam-based analysis method with the help of additional markers. One suggestive QTL and 2 genome-wide significant QTLs were detected from the genomic data. Linkage map was constructed by choosing markers based on their position in a composite linkage map (from GRASP website) and establishing the linkage among those markers with the help of Crimap version 2.4 (Green *et al.*, 1990). The QTLs was then detected from the genome scan by a two-stage linear-regression method (Knott *et al.*, 1994) utilizing QTL Express (Seaton *et al.*, 2002).

Chapter 03

Materials and Method

3.1 Materials

To achieve a chromosome level assembly and to perform the comparative genome and proteome analyses, a variety of tools and hardware for data generation and analysis is required.

3.1.1 Technical infrastructure

Data generation and analysis were performed using different hardware settings and a variety of software. A brief overview of hardware and software applications is given below.

3.1.1.1 Hardware

Various applications require hardware settings dependent on resource demands and Input size. Here, mainly three different hardware platforms were used, Small scripts and quick analyses were performed on a personal desktop computer equipped with six cores (one thread per core) and up to 8 GB of RAM. Computationally more demanding software was run on a high- performance computing cluster (HPC) with configurations of up to 10 nodes with 20 threads and 256 GB RAM. The web server is hosted on a powerful machine with sixteen cores (two threads per core) and up to 128 GB of RAM (Table 1), which supplies sufficient resources for web-based applications such as the Apollo genome annotation browser.

3.1.1.2 Software

Several computational tools were employed to perform the *in silico* analyses:

1. For cleaning and trimming of the data set-
 - a. BFC (Pevzner *et al.*, 2001)
 - b. Trimmomatic (Bolger *et al.*, 2014)
2. For Mapping of raw data against a reference genome-
 - a. Burrows-Wheeler Aligner BWA (Li and Durbin, 2009)
 - b. Samtools (Li *et al.*, 2009)
3. For genome assembly-
 - a. AbySS (Jackman *et al.*, 2017)
 - b. SOAPdenovo2 (Luo *et al.*, 2012)
 - c. MaSuRCA (Zimin *et al.*, 2013)
 - d. Platanus (Kajitani *et al.*, 2014)

4. For the construction of chromosome level assembly-
 - a. SSPACE (Boetzer *et al.*, 2011)
 - b. Pilon (Walker *et al.*, 2014)
 - c. MUMmer (Delcher *et al.*, 1999)
 - d. Minimap2 (Li, 2018)
 - e. JCVI ALLMAPS (Tang *et al.*, 2015)
5. For repeat contents analysis-
 - a. RepeatMasker (Tarailo-Graovac and Chen, 2009)
 - b. RepeatModeler (Flynn *et al.*, 2020)
 - c. RepeatScout (Price *et al.*, 2005)
6. For gene prediction-
 - a. AUGUSTUS (Stanke and Morgenstern 2005)
 - b. MAKER (Cantarel *et al.*, 2008)
7. For protein prediction and annotation-
 - a. InterProScan (Quevillon *et al.*, 2005)
 - b. Pannzer2 (Törönen *et al.*, 2018)

3.2 Method

3.2.1 Data collection:

A sample of *Catla catla* was collected from Halda River, Hathazari, Chattogram in 2020 by the Halda River Research Laboratory, University of Chittagong. Previously sequenced raw data of Catla from Halda River, was submitted to the NCBI which can be found in the Data Description section in detail. In the previous year, Halda River Research Laboratory assembled a scaffold level genome with that raw data. The goal was to reassemble the genome at the chromosome level for a better understanding of the genetic variation of the Catla from the Halda River.

3.2.2 Genome assembly

3.2.2.1 Genome assembly and chromosome orientation

After collecting the raw data from NCBI, cleaning and trimming of the data set were done for the removal of adapters and other sequencing errors, and various other preprocessing was done before genome assembly. BFC (Pevzner *et al.*, 2001) and Trimmomatic (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) were used for this purpose. The BWA-MEM algorithm from Burrows-Wheeler Aligner (BWA) and Samtools (Li

et al., 2009) was employed to map the raw data with the *Gallus gallus* reference genome to check the mapping quality and overall homogeneity.

Multiple genome assemblers were used to get the best results from one of them. AbySS (Jackman *et al.*, 2017), SOAPdenovo2 (Luo *et al.*, 2012), MaSuRCA (Zimin *et al.*, 2013) and Platanus (Kajitani *et al.*, 2014) were used for genome assembly with Illumina raw data. SSPACE (Boetzer *et al.*, 2011), Pilon (Walker *et al.*, 2014), MUMmer (Delcher *et al.*, 1999), minimap2 (Li, 2018) and a custom made polishing script with Python and Shell script were used to polish up the assembled genome with the help of reference genome. In this case *Danio rerio* (Zebrafish), *Cyprinus carpio* (Common Carp), *Catla catla* (CIFA Catla, India) and *Labeo rohita* (Rohu) were used as reference genome to polish up the assembled genome and construction of chromosome level assembly. Finally, reference genome with MUMmer (Delcher *et al.*, 1999), minimap (Li, 2018), JCVI ALLMAPS (Tang *et al.*, 2015) were used to align, map, order and orient the chromosome to create a superior chromosome level assembly which was vital for the further research on GWAS, specific traits or attributes, and proteomic analysis.

After genome assembly, ABACAS (Aseefa *et al.*, 2009) along with MUMmer (nucmer for nucleotide) was used for anchoring, and aligning scaffolds to chromosome with the help of reference chromosome. ABACAS is intended to rapidly contiguate (align, order, orientate), visualize and design primers to close gaps on shotgun assembled contigs based on a reference sequence. ABACAS uses MUMmer to find alignment positions and identify syntenies of assembled contigs against the reference. The output is then processed to generate a pseudomolecule taking overlapping contigs and gaps in to account. ABACAS generates a comparison file that can be used to visualize ordered and oriented contigs in ACT. Synteny is represented by red bars where colour intensity decreases with lower values of percent identity between comparable blocks. Information on contigs such as the orientation, percent identity, coverage and overlap with other contigs can also be visualized by loading the outputted feature file on ACT. The fasta files containing the reference (in a single fasta format) and query (contigs) was given as input.

The JCVI bioinformatics utility library is a collection of Python libraries and ALLMAPS is one of them. The ordering and orientation of genomic scaffolds to reconstruct chromosomes is essential during de novo genome assembly. This process is often assisted by various mapping techniques. Because each map provides a unique line of evidence, a combination of multiple maps can greatly improve the accuracy of the resulting chromosomal assemblies. ALLMAPS is

capable of computing a scaffold order that maximizes the colinearity to a collection of maps, including genetic, physical, or comparative maps into the final chromosome build. We highlight several salient features of ALLMAPS.

3.2.2.2 Assembly quality assurance and benchmarking

The quality of the assembled genome was checked with reference genome using QUAST (Gurevich *et al.*, 2013) and BUSCO (Seppey *et al.*, 2019). QUAST gave the homology of assembled genome with reference genome and BUSCO (Seppey *et al.*, 2019) benchmarked the gene completeness.

3.2.3 Functional genome analysis

3.2.3.1 Repeat elements and divergent determination:

RepeatMasker (Tarailo-Graovac and Chen, 2009), RepeatModeler (Flynn *et al.*, 2020), RepeatScout (Price *et al.*, 2005) with RepBase (Bao *et al.*, 2015) were used to determine the repeat elements and divergent of the genome.

3.2.3.2 Gene prediction

Ab initio gene prediction took place with AUGUSTUS (Stanke and Morgenstern 2005) and MAKER (Cantarel *et al.*, 2008) pipeline to carry out all complete and partial genes for further process and use.

3.2.3.3 Protein prediction and annotation

InterProScan (Quevillon *et al.*, 2005) and Pannzer2 (Törönen *et al.*, 2018) were used to annotate the proteins, identify the domains and protein function and match gene ontology with public databases.

3.2.3.4 Quantitative trait loci analysis

Important traits related to egg production, muscle development and immunity were determined and assessed with quantitative trait analysis using NCBI, Uniprot database, custom machine learning trained algorithms and existing bioinformatics tools (i.e. BLASTx, Blast2Go, BLASTp, tBLASTn,). Comparative trait analysis was done with relative indigenous and commercial species.

3.2.3.5 GWAS and Pathway analysis of economically important traits

From biochemical reaction to cellular and molecular function, influencing the physiological pathway, metabolism and expression of phenotypes of any gene involved to economically important traits were analyzed with NCBI, KEGG, Public gene ontology database and computational biology approach.

3.2.3.6 Data visualization

Custom R packages with cloud computing web servers were used to visualize final data sets.

Chapter 04

Results

4.1 Chromosome level assembled genome:

A chromosome level genome was constructed with 25 pair chromosomes, 1 mitochondrial circular DNA and 2200 unplaced scaffolds. The total size of the genome was 1059564832 base pairs, N50 of 33.29 Mbp, and maximum sized scaffold with 43.29 Mbp, providing a high quality assembled genome with very few short fragments on the genome. GC content was 36.50 percent (Table 1) (Figure 9-12). The used reference genomes were Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) Reference genome (BioSample: SAMN06930106, BioProject: PRJNA11776, GenBank assembly accession: GCA_000002035.4), Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) Reference genome (BioSample: SAMN17005855, BioProject: PRJNA682709, GenBank assembly accession: GCA_018340385.1), and Indian CIFA Catla (BioSample: SAMN123900082, BioProject: PRJNA557138, GenBank assembly accession: GCA_012976165.1)

Table 1: Genome statistics

	Catla from Halda	Zebrafish Reference (GCA_000002035.4)	Common Carp Reference (GCA_018340385.1)	Indian CIFA Catla (GCA_012976165.1)
Total ungapped length	1015 Mbp	1368 Mbp	1672 Mbp	1019 Mbp
Number of sequences	2225	1923	6701	13523
Number of bases	1059564832	1373454788	1680134903	1019782285
N50	33.29 Mbp (25 Chr)	42.11 Mbp (50 Chr)	25.46 Mbp (50 Chr)	1.9 Mbp
L50	9	14	24	353
Min base	16738	650	506	1431
Max base	43.29 Mbp	75.27 Mbp	48.11 Mbp	0.6 Mbp
Unplaced	2200	1872	6650	13523

Figure 9: Total ungapged length in different genomes

Figure 10: Number sequences in different genomes

Figure 11: Number of bases in different genomes

Figure 12: N50 of different genomes

4.2 Gene completeness:

By employing sets of Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs from OrthoDB (www.orthodb.org) of Eukaryotes and Actinopterygii (Figure 13-15), BUSCO gene completeness benchmark used to perform a gene completeness check and the output was as follows (Table 2):

Table 2: Gene completeness report

	Eukaryota	Actinopterygii
Completeness in %	C:93.8% [S:91.8%,D:2.0%],F:5.9%,M:0.3%	C:92.2% [S:91.0%,D:1.2%],F:3.3%,M:4.5%
Complete BUSCOs (C)	239	3355
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (S)	234	3313
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs (D)	5	42
Fragmented BUSCOs (F)	15	120
Missing BUSCOs (M)	0	165
Total BUSCO groups searched	255	3640

Figure 13: Completeness result from different lineages

Figure 14: Complete BUSCOs from eukaryota

Figure 15: Complete BUSCOs from actinopterygii

4.3 Repeat elements on the genome:

A total of 24% percent of repeats was found on the genome. On all the repeated content there were 5% retroelements, 1.53% LINES, 3.25% LTR elements, 14.20% DNA transposons, 1.46% satellites, 1.80% simple repeats were predicted (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Repeat elements on the genome

4.4 Functional gene prediction and protein annotation:

A total of 49028 genes were predicted with AUGUSTUS. A protein coding region was found where a total of more than 16000 gene ontology was detected with their respective pathway. Protein annotation with gene ontology and pathway mapping was done by eggNOG-Mapper (Cantalapiedra *et al.*, 2021) and Pannzer2 tools with the dependency on BLASTx, BLASTn, tBLASTn, KEGG database, NCBI Gene Ontology, Entrez Direct, Ensembl and EBI ENA database. A total of 27889 genes were placed in 25 chromosomes, among which 24065 genes were annotated (Figure 18-19), 16768 genes were identified with gene ontology, and 16139 genes were found with KEGG pathways. 21139 genes of all the identified genes couldn't be placed in any chromosome (Figure 17), where 12607 of the unplaced genes were annotated, 3395 genes were identified with gene ontology, and 6374 genes were identified with KEGG pathways (Table 3).

Table 3: Number of genes per chromosome:

Chromosome	Genes	Annotated	Gene Ontology	KEGG Pathway
1	1169	1006	754	721
2	1321	1104	791	785

3	1353	1131	772	765
4	967	748	510	512
5	1547	1318	965	907
6	1154	994	762	724
7	1475	1209	875	853
8	1205	1001	759	711
9	1177	952	670	632
10	1038	870	650	618
11	884	722	562	539
12	970	828	642	595
13	1107	907	697	637
14	955	775	587	563
15	1084	843	579	596
16	1410	1115	755	755
17	1194	986	740	676
18	1043	815	561	538
19	1116	915	677	636
20	1092	922	707	663
21	995	820	626	594
22	894	710	432	462
23	951	826	596	595
24	875	689	511	482
25	913	757	573	563
Total genes in Chromosomes	27889	24065	16768	16139
Unplaced genes	21139	12607	3395	6374
Total	49028	35572	20148	22496

Figure 17: Number of genes per chromosome

Figure 18: Genes in Chromosome

Figure 19: Unplaced genes

4.5 Comparative genome and proteome analysis:

4.5.1 Comparison between *C. catla* and *L. rohita* at chromosome level:

From the assembly of *Catla catla*, a total of 22963 annotated genes were placed along 25 chromosomes while the chromosome level assembly of *Labeo rohita* (GCA_022985175.1) annotated 26707 genes placed in 25 chromosomes (Table 4) (Figure 20).

Table 4: Number of genes per chromosome of *C. catla* and *L. rohita*

Chromosome	<i>Catla catla</i>	<i>Labeo rohita</i>
1	1006	1259
2	1104	1313
3	1131	1475
4	748	915
5	1318	1439
6	994	1130
7	1209	1426
8	1001	1152
9	952	983
10	870	1013
11	722	878
12	828	919
13	907	977
14	775	880
15	843	987
16	1115	1267
17	986	1006
18	815	864
19	915	1063
20	922	1055
21	820	1089
22	710	1025
23	826	964
24	689	722
25	757	906

Figure 20: Number of genes per chromosome of *C. catla* and *L. rohita*

4.5.2 Comparison of orthologous genes and proteins of five cyprinid species:

To elucidate orthologous relationships for the *C. catha* annotated genes, they were compared with four other diploid cyprinid species: *Labeo calbasu*, *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus cirrhosus*, and *Danio rerio* by employing OrthoVenn (Wang *et al.*, 2015). OrthoVenn2 generates clusters of proteins each cluster consists of orthologs or paralogs from different species. The overlapping cluster means the cluster contains proteins from different species. In Figure 22 the overlapping cluster numbers refer to the cluster numbers that were shared between species. Orthologous genes shared among these species were delineated through a Venn diagram (Figure 22). The orthologous gene family analysis in diploid cyprinids resulted in a total of 144,155 clusters (*C. Catla*, 25860; *D. rerio* 17358; *L. rohita* 26142; *L. calbasu*, 37749; and *C. cirrhosus*, 37019 orthologous clusters) (Figure 22) A total of 13,040 orthologs are shared by all five species (Figure 22), with 306 species-specific gene clusters of *C. catla*.

Table 5: Counts of clusters in five cyprinid species genome.

Species	Proteins	Clusters	Singletons
<i>Danio rerio</i>	24544	17385	2839
<i>Catla catla</i>	49028	25860	19973

<i>Labeo rohita</i>	47568	26142	18083
<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	68803	37749	25822
<i>Cirrhinus cirrhosus</i>	59599	37019	17873

Figure 21: Counts of clusters in five cyprinid species genome.

Figure 22: Comparative genomics of *C. catla*: Venn diagram showing orthologous gene clusters among five diploid cyprinid species, *D. rerio*, *C. catla*, *L. rohita*, *L. calbasu*, *C. cirrhosus*

Figure 23: Comparative genomics of *C. catla*: The occurrence table shows the occurrence pattern of shared orthologous groups among five diploid cyprinid species, *D. rerio*, *C. catla*, *L. rohita*, *L. calbasu*, *C. cirrhosus*

Figure 24: Comparative genomics of *C. catla*: Cluster overlaps showing orthologous genes and protein clusters among five diploid cyprinid species, *D. rerio*, *C. catla*, *L. rohita*, *L. calbasu*, *C. cirrhosus*

4.6 Ascertaining some candidate genes of *C. catla* from Halda River related to unique and important traits:

Catla is one of the native major carps, that contributes a lot to the country's annual fish production and that helps a great to meet up the dietary protein demand of the population as well as boosting up the economy by creating employment. Taking into account all of the above, the Catla from Halda River contributes even more by producing naturally spawned fish seeds. Regarding these facts, the genetic features of the Catla from Halda River is required revealing. The fish genomics related to the candidate gene approach is now being used to recognize molecular mechanisms that have different expressions of growth, reproduction, feeding behavior, and disease resistance (Zonaed Siddiki et al., 2020).

Genes that are related to different important traits in *C. catla* are given below:

4.6.1 Growth and body weight: Genes from somatotropic axis and transforming growth factor superfamily such as growth hormone receptor (GHR), growth hormone (GH), insulin-like growth factors (IGF-I and II), associated carrier proteins (IGFBPs) and receptors are primary candidate genes (Ulloa *et al.*, 2011). Myostatin (MSTN), also known as growth/differentiation factor-8 (GDF-8) also influences the growth (McPherron *et al.*, 1997). Myogenic regulatory factors (MRFs) (myogenin, Myod, myf-5, myf-6) constitute a small family of transcriptional factors, called the Myod gene complex, involved in myogenesis and are expressed exclusively in the skeletal muscle (Atchley *et al.*, 1994). Follistatin (fst) is also an essential gene for fish growth (Phillips and de Kretser, 1998). Other growth genes studied in fish are those of the calpain-calpastatin (CAST) (Goll *et al.*, 2003). Several candidate genes involved in body weight are as follows: The genes *cilp2*, *mef2b* (myocyte-specific enhancer factor 2B), *rxfank* (regulatory factor X-associated ankyrin-containing protein), *rab6b* (Ras-related protein Rab-6B), *cep19* (19-kDa centrosomal protein), *dhcr24* (24-dehydrocholesterol reductase), *lmo4* (LIM domain transcription factor), *sgta* (small glutamine-rich tetratricopeptide repeat-containing protein alpha) (Table 6)(Yassumoto *et al.*, 2020).

Table 6: Genes that are related to growth and body weight in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
GHR	8	The soluble form (GHBP) acts as a reservoir of growth hormone in plasma and may be a modulator/inhibitor of GH signaling.
GH	21	
IGF1	7	

IGFBP2	6, 9	IGF-binding proteins prolong the half-life of the IGFs and have been shown to either inhibit or stimulate the growth promoting effects of the IGFs on cell culture. They alter the interaction of IGFs with their cell surface receptors
MSTN	9	Acts specifically as a negative regulator of skeletal muscle growth. May down-regulate muscle-specific transcription factors such as myod and myog.
MYOD1	25	May act as a transcriptional activator that promotes transcription of muscle-specific target genes and plays a role in muscle differentiation.
MYF5	4	
MYF6	4	Involved in muscle differentiation (myogenic factor). Induces fibroblasts to differentiate into myoblasts. Probable sequence specific DNA-binding protein (By similarity).
FST	5, 10	inhibits the transformation of growth factor-b proteins and is a known regulator of amniote myogenesis
CAST	21	Regulates a wide range of physiological processes including protein turnover and growth, cell cycle progression, and myoblast differentiation.
CLIP2	5	Expressing cartilage intermediate layer protein.
MEF2B	22	Activates transcription, and involved in muscle-specific and/or growth factor-related transcription.
RFXANK	22	
RAB6B	2, 6	
CEP19	22	Required for ciliation. Recruits the RABL2B GTPase to the ciliary base to initiate ciliation.
DHCR24	20	Catalyzes the reduction of the delta-24 double bond of sterol intermediates during cholesterol biosynthesis and Also protects against amyloid-beta peptide-induced apoptosis.
SGTA	11	
LMO4	6	Transcription cofactor. Plays a role in establishing motor neuron identity,

4.6.2 Food intake: Feeding behaviors in fishes are controlled by the feeding centers of the brain which are influenced by the hormones secreted by the brain and the periphery (Volkoff, 2016). Genes associated with food intake are: *prrt4*, *tmem53*, *rbm28*, *lrrc4*, *hgf*, *cacng3*, *mical3*, *zbed1*, and *npy2r* (Table 7) (Ding *et al.*, 2021).

Table 7: Genes that are related to food intake in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
PRRT4	4, 18	Predicted to be located in membrane. Predicted to be integral component of membrane.
TMEM53	2	Predicted to be located in membrane. Predicted to be integral component of membrane
RBM28	18	
LRRC4	4, 18	
HGF	4, 18	Predicted to enable signaling receptor binding activity. Acts upstream of or within cerebellar granule cell differentiation and neuron migration. Predicted to enable channel regulator activity and voltage-gated calcium channel activity. Predicted to be involved in several processes, including neurotransmitter receptor internalization; neurotransmitter receptor transport etc.
CACNG3	1	Predicted to enable FAD binding activity; actin binding activity; and oxidoreductase activity, expressed in floor plate; hindbrain nucleus; octaval nerve motor nucleus etc.
ZBED1	6, 12, 17, 22, 23	
NPY2R	1	Enables neuropeptide binding activity, expressed in several structures, including digestive system; eye; heart; immune system; and muscle.

4.6.3 Osmoregulation: Osmoregulation is one of the most important physiological process in fishes. Genes associated with this process are as follows: *arrdc3*, *gsta4*, *slc12a2*, *slc12a5*, *txnip*, *gstt1*, *gstz1* (Table 8) (Zhu *et al.*, 2021).

Table 8: Genes that are related to osmoregulation in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
ARRDC3	5,10	Predicted to be involved in protein transport.

		Predicted to be active in cytoplasm. Is expressed in liver.
GSTA4	13	
SLC12A2	1, 8	Cation-chloride cotransporter which mediates the electroneutral transport of chloride, potassium and/or sodium ions across the membrane. Plays a vital role in the regulation of ionic balance and cell volume.
SLC12A5	6	Mediates electroneutral potassium-chloride cotransport in mature neurons and is required for neuronal Cl ⁻ homeostasis. As major extruder of intracellular chloride, it establishes the low neuronal Cl ⁻ levels required for chloride influx after binding of GABA-A and glycine to their receptors, with subsequent hyperpolarization and neuronal inhibition (By similarity).
TXNIP	19	
GSTT1	14, 21	Conjugation of reduced glutathione to a wide number of exogenous and endogenous hydrophobic electrophiles. Also binds steroids, bilirubin, carcinogens and numerous organic anions. Has dichloromethane dehalogenase activity.
GSTZ1	17	Enables glutathione transferase activity. Predicted to be involved in L-phenylalanine catabolic process and glutathione metabolic process.
NHE2	19	Involved in pH regulation to eliminate acids generated by active metabolism or to counter adverse environmental conditions.

4.6.4 Vision: For vision in fish, opsin genes are associated with photoreceptive molecule rhodopsin; which typically acts as the light sensors (Sakmar et al., 2002). They are as follows: rh2, sws2, cyp27c1 (Musilova *et al.*, 2021), hcfc1, gnl31 (Table 9) (Cortesi *et al.*, 2015).

Table 9: Genes that are related to vision in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
RH2	6	
SWS2	11	Producing visual pigments that are light-absorbing molecules that mediate vision. They

		consist of an apoprotein, opsin, covalently linked to cis-retinal.
CYP27C1	6	Helps to see in turbid water, expressed in several structures, including immature eye; margin; neural tube; retina; and yolk syncytial layer. Predicted to enable transcription coactivator activity. Acts upstream of or within brain development. Predicted to be part of histone methyltransferase complex.
HCFC1	8, 11	
GNL3L	11	Predicted to enable GTP binding activity. Acts upstream of or within rRNA processing. Predicted to be active in nucleolus.
SIX6	13, 20	May be involved in eye development.

4.6.5 Gonad development: Genes associated with the metabolic processes related to gonad development are: *Cyp17a1*, *Cyp11a1*, *Dhrs3*, *Dhrs9*, *Ece1*, and *Hsd11b2*. Genes involved in muscle contraction adjacent to reproductive organs are: *Anxa6*, *Atp1a1*, *Myl9*, and *Tpm1*. Genes encoding extracellular matrix constituents are: *Sox10* and *Tbx1*. Genes responsible for reproductive fluid constitution and hydration during spawning are: *Ank1*, *Agpat9*, *Canx*, *Cav2*, *Dgat1*, *Gars*, *Glx5*, and *Slc39a1*(Table 10) (Rolland *et al.*, 2009).

Table 10: Genes that are related to gonad development in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
CYP17A1	13	Conversion of pregnenolone and progesterone to their 17-alpha-hydroxylated products and subsequently to dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA). A cytochrome P450 monooxygenase that catalyzes the side-chain hydroxylation and cleavage of cholesterol to pregnenolone, the precursor of most steroid hormones.
CYP11A1	25	
DHRS3	11	Catalyzes the reduction of all-trans-retinal to all-trans-retinol in the presence of NADPH
DHRS9	22	Enables NAD-retinol dehydrogenase activity. Acts upstream of or within several processes, including animal organ development; pectoral fin morphogenesis; and retinoid metabolic process.
ECE1	11	Converts big endothelin-1 to endothelin-1.

HSD11B2	7	Plays a key role by catalyzing the oxidation of 11beta-hydroxytestosterone to 11-ketotestosterone, the major fish androgen, that activates androgen receptor transcriptional activity.
ANXA6	14	May associate with CD21. May regulate the release of Ca ²⁺ from intracellular stores.
ATP1A1	9	
MYL9	6, 23	Predicted to enable calcium ion binding activity. Binds to actin filaments in muscle and non-muscle cells. Plays a central role, in association with the troponin complex, in the calcium dependent regulation of vertebrate striated muscle contraction.
TPM1	7	Predicted to enable DNA-binding transcription factor activity, RNA polymerase II-specific and RNA polymerase II cis-regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding activity. Involved in olfactory bulb development.
SOX10	3	Probable transcriptional regulator involved in developmental processes.
TBX1	5	Attaches integral membrane proteins to cytoskeletal elements.
ANK1	5, 17, 21	Converts glycerol-3-phosphate to 1-acyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphate (lysophosphatidic acid or LPA) by incorporating an acyl moiety.
AGPAT9	5, 21	Calcium-binding protein that interacts with newly synthesized monoglucosylated glycoproteins in the endoplasmic reticulum.
CANX	-	May act as a scaffolding protein within caveolar membranes. Interacts directly with G-protein alpha subunits and can functionally regulate their activity.
CAV2	25	Predicted to enable CARD domain binding activity and oligopeptide binding activity. Acts upstream of or within defense response to other organisms; hatching behavior; and regulation of MAPK cascade.
DGAT1	16, 19	
GARS	24	
GLRX5	20	Involved in mitochondrial iron-sulfur (Fe/S) cluster transfer

4.6.6 Egg quality: Fish egg quality refers to the ability of the egg to be fertilized and subsequently develop into a normal embryo. The process of the creation of a viable and normal embryo depends on environmental, biological factors, oogenetic factors (Brooks *et al.*, 1997) as well as on the genetic factors (Su *et al.*, 1997). Some essential genes associated with egg quality are: tLe1, lrtm1, alg2, gtf2b, fgd5, pdgfra, cul5, bmp7, vwf, nek1, casz1, khk, lamb2, kif4a, obscn, hcfc1, pdcL3, apob, tgfbr2, mcf2L, dcps, gmcl1 (Table 11) (Bonnet *et al.*, 2007).

Table 11: Genes that are related to egg quality in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
TLE1	14	Transcriptional corepressor that binds to a number of transcription factors.
LRTM1	8	
ALG2	16	Predicted to enable alpha-1,3-mannosyltransferase activity and glycolipid mannosyltransferase activity.
GTF2B	2	Predicted to enable several functions, including RNA polymerase II core promoter sequence-specific DNA binding activity; RNA polymerase II general transcription initiation factor activity; and TBP-class protein binding activity.
FGD5	6	
PDGFRA	20	Acts as a cell-surface receptor for pdgfa, pdgfb and pdgfc and plays an essential role in the regulation of embryonic development, cell proliferation, survival and chemotaxis.
CUL5	15, 21	Involved in cell cycle control and autophagy.
BMP7	11, 23	
VWF	16, 18	Dorsalizes early vertebrate embryonic tissues by binding to ventralizing TGF-beta family bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) and sequestering them in latent complexes.
NEK1	7, 20	Predicted to enable protein serine/threonine kinase activity. Acts upstream of or within cilium assembly and cranial skeletal system development.
CASZ1	10, 20, 23	Predicted to enable DNA-binding transcription factor activity, RNA polymerase II-specific and RNA polymerase II transcription regulatory region

KHK	17	sequence-specific DNA binding activity. Predicted to enable ketohexokinase activity.
LAMB2	23	Predicted to enable integrin binding activity. Predicted to be an extracellular matrix structural constituent.
KIF4A	21	
OBSCN	8, 24	Predicted to enable protein kinase activity. Predicted to act upstream of or within muscle organ development.
HCFC1	8, 11	Predicted to enable transcription coactivator activity. Acts upstream of or within brain development.
PDCL3	9	Involved in positive regulation of gene expression. Acts upstream of or within angiogenesis.
APOB	17, 20	Essential for proper chromosome segregation, post-replicative DNA repair, and the prevention of inappropriate recombination between repetitive regions.
TGFBR2	16, 19	Regulates a plethora of physiological and pathological processes including cell cycle arrest in epithelial and hematopoietic cells, control of mesenchymal cell proliferation and differentiation, wound healing, extracellular matrix production, immunosuppression and carcinogenesis.
MCF2L	1, 9	
DCPS	10	Decapping scavenger enzyme that catalyzes the cleavage of a residual cap structure following the degradation of mRNAs.
GMCL1	10	Predicted to act upstream of or within germ cell development. Is expressed in blastomere; ovary; and testis.

4.6.7 Immune related: Immune related genes present in liver cells are *mr1*, *hsp90b1* (Gao *et al.*, 2021b); some innate immune related genes are *tlr2*, *tlr3*, *tlr5*, *tlr21*, *nod1*, *nod2*, *apaf1*, *ciita*, *cfi*, *cd59*, *cxcl12*, *cxcl14*, *cxcr4*, *mr1*, *hsp90b1* (Table 12) (Gao *et al.*, 2012).

Table 12: Genes that are related to immunity in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
TLR2	1	mediate the innate immune response to bacterial

		lipoproteins and other microbial cell wall components.
TLR3	-	Key component of innate and adaptive immunity. TLRs (Toll-like receptors) control host immune response against pathogens through recognition of molecular patterns specific to microorganisms.
TLR5	20	Pattern recognition receptor (PRR) located on the cell surface that participates in the activation of innate immunity and inflammatory response.
TLR21	16	Predicted to enable signaling receptor activity.
NOD1	16	Predicted to enable CARD domain binding activity and oligopeptide binding activity.
NOD2	7	Helps to detect bacterial peptidoglycan fragments and other danger signals and plays an important role in gastrointestinal immunity
APAF1	4	Mediates the cytochrome c-dependent autocatalytic activation of pro-caspase-9 (Apaf-3), leading to the activation of caspase-3 and apoptosis.
CIITA	-	Essential for transcriptional activity of the HLA class II promoter; activation is via the proximal promoter.
CFI	23	Plays an essential role in regulating the immune response by controlling all complement pathways.
CD59	7	Potent inhibitor of the complement membrane attack complex (MAC) action. Acts at or after the C5b-8 stage of MAC assembly.
CXCL12	13, 22	Activates the C-X-C chemokine receptor cxcr4 to induce a rapid and transient rise in the level of intracellular calcium ions, and chemotaxis.
CXCL14	14	Potent chemoattractant for neutrophils, and weaker for dendritic cells. Not chemotactic for T-cells, B-cells, monocytes, natural killer cells or granulocytes.
CXCR4	6, 9	Receptor for the C-X-C chemokine CXCL12/SDF-1 that transduces a signal by increasing intracellular calcium ion levels and enhancing MAPK1/MAPK3 activation.
MR1	2	High affinity receptor for melatonin. The activity of this receptor is mediated by pertussis toxin sensitive G proteins that inhibits adenylate cyclase activity.
HSP90B1	4	Functions in the processing and transport of secreted

4.6.8 Nerve conduction and migration: Genes associated with nerve conduction are *slc25a22*, *sez6*, *ncam*, *rims2*, *fgf13*, *cacnb3*, (Gao et al., 2021b) and genes associated with migration are *acox1*, *adra1b*, *mtmr7* (Table 13) (Gao et al., 2021b).

Table 13: Genes that are related to nerve conduction and migration in *C. catla*.

Gene name	Chromosome	Function
SLC25A22	6, 7, 23, 25	Predicted to enable L-aspartate transmembrane transporter activity and L-glutamate transmembrane transporter activity and to be involved in L-glutamate transmembrane transport
SEZ6	1, 8, 10, 15	May play a role in cell-cell recognition and in neuronal membrane signaling.
NCAM1	12, 15, 21	Involved in neuron-neuron adhesion, neurite fasciculation, outgrowth of neurites, etc.
NCAM2	1, 9	May play important roles in selective fasciculation and zone-to-zone projection of the primary olfactory axons.
RIMS2	16, 19	Rab effector involved in exocytosis. May act as scaffold protein. Plays a role in dendrite formation by melanocytes.
FGF13	10, 14	Predicted to enable sodium channel regulator activity. Predicted to be involved in regulation of voltage-gated sodium channel activity. Predicted to act upstream of or within nervous system development. Predicted to be located in several cellular components, including filopodium; growth cone; and microtubule.
CACNB3	23	
ACOX1	-	Involved in the initial and rate-limiting step of peroxisomal beta-oxidation of straight-chain saturated and unsaturated very-long-chain fatty acids.
ADRA1B	14, 21, 24	
MTMR7	1, 14	Predicted to enable phosphatidylinositol-3-phosphatase activity. Predicted to be involved in phosphatidylinositol dephosphorylation. Predicted to act upstream of or within dephosphorylation.

Chapter 05

Discussion

5.1 Chromosome level assembly and gene annotation

From the achieved genome assembly up to chromosome level, the genome size (number of bases) of Catla from Halda River was **1,059,564,832** base pairs, which larger than the Indian CIFA Catla (GCA_012976165.1) reference genome but smaller than the other two reference genome (Zebrafish Reference genome (GCA_000002035.4) and Common Carp Reference genome (GCA_018340385.1)). The order of the genome sizes is: 1,680,134,903 > 1,373,454,788 > **1,059,564,832** > 1,019,782,285 base pairs belonging to Common Carp, Zebrafish, catla from Halda River, and Indian CIFA Catla respectively. The assembly of catla from Halda River had a total of **2225** sequences which was only higher than that of the Zebrafish but lower than that of both common carp and Indian CIFA catla, as smaller number of sequences indicates better assembly quality. The order of the number of sequences is: 1923 < **2225** < 6701 < 13523 belonging to Zebrafish, Catla from Halda River, Common Carp, and Indian CIFA Catla respectively. The assembly of Catla from Halda River had N50 of **33.29 Mbp** which was second highest among the four assembly. The order for the N50 is: 42.11 > **33.29** > 25.46 > 1.9 Mbp belonging to Zebrafish, catla from Halda River, Common Carp, and Indian CIFA Catla respectively. The assembly of Catla from Halda River had the lowest L50 which was **9** while the L50 of the other three reference genome of Zebrafish, Common Carp, and Indian CIFA Catla were 14, 24, and 353 respectively. The assembly of Catla from Halda River had a total ungapped length of **1015 Mbp** which was the lowest while the other three reference genome of Zebrafish, Common Carp, and Indian CIFA Catla had a total of 1368, 1672, and 1019 Mbp ungapped length respectively.

The BUSCO gene completeness report showed that a total of **239 (93.8%)** complete BUSCOs and 15 (5.9%) fragmented BUSCOs (F) were detected out of 255 BUSCO groups from eukaryotic lineage, among those complete 239 BUSCOs, 234 (91.8%) were complete single-copy BUSCOs (S) and 5 (2%) were complete duplicated BUSCOs. A total of **3355 (92.2%)** complete BUSCOs (C), 120 (3.3%) fragmented BUSCOs (F), were detected out of 255 BUSCO groups from actinopterygii lineage, among those 3355 complete BUSCOs, 234 (91.8%) were complete single-copy BUSCOs (S) and 5 (2%) were complete duplicated BUSCOs besides 165 (4.5%) BUSCOs were missing (M) from the actinopterygii lineage. A total of 24% percent of repeats was also found on the genome.

A total of **49028** genes were predicted, 35572 genes were functionally annotated, 20148 gene ontology were found, and 22496 genes with KEGG pathways were detected. Out of 49028 genes, a total of **27889 (56.88%)** genes were placed along 25 (n) chromosomes and 21139 (43.12%) remained unplaced. Highest number of predicted genes (1547) and annotated genes (1318) belonged to chromosome 5.

5.2 Comparative genome and proteome analysis:

The comparative study of *C. catla* was done with four other cyprinid species e.g. *Danio rerio*, *Labeo rohita*, *Labeo catla*, and *Cirrhinus cirrhosus*. *C. catla* shared 25860 clusters with other four species and possessed 19973 singleton genes for which no orthologs could be found in any of the other species.

5.3 Determination of some candidate genes of *C. catla* from Halda River related to unique and important traits :

A total of 108 genes were determined for several important traits. Out of 108 genes, 18 genes were associated with growth and body weight, 9 genes were associated with food intake/ feeding behavior, 8 genes were associated with osmoregulation, 6 genes associated with vision, 20 genes were associated with gonad development, 22 genes were associated with egg quality, 15 genes were associated with immunity, and 10 genes were associated with nerve conduction and migration almost all of the 25 chromosomes.

Chapter 06

Conclusion

Despite its importance to aquaculture, the catla has only recently been studied using modern molecular techniques. In this study, a chromosomal-level genome assembly for the Catla from Halda was generated, which has been an economically important fish in Bangladesh. The genome assembly possesses a much better quality, completeness, and accuracy based on multiple evaluations. Gene prediction, functional annotation, and evolutionary analysis provided new insights into the genomic structure and functions related to several important traits. This assembled sequences of catla fish will also offer a valuable genetic resource to support extensive fisheries and artificial breeding programs, and thereby allows for effective disease management, growth improvement, and discovering new drugs in *C. catla*.

Chapter 07

References

- Abdelrahman, H., ElHady, M., Alcivar-Warren, A., Allen, S., Al-Tobasei, R., Bao, L., Beck, B., Blackburn, H., Bosworth, B., and Buchanan, J., 2017. Aquaculture genomics, genetics and breeding in the United States: current status, challenges, and priorities for future research. *BMC genomics*, 18 (1), 1–23.
- Ahmed, M., Khanom, R., and Mostafa, M., 2003. Population dynamics of *Clupisoma garua* (Siluriformes: Schilbeidae) from the river Jamuna. *BANGLADESH JOURNAL OF ZOOLOGY*, 31 (1), 7–14.
- Akhtar, N., 1991. The Northern Areas (Pakistan). Fisheries profile, feasible sites for trout culture and an overall sector development perspective. *Report for Project PAK/91/008. Rome FAO*.
- Akter, S., Asek, A. A., Bhuiyan, M. A. B., Rahman, S. S., Siddiki, A. Z., Kibria, M. M. 2021 (a). *Labeo rohita* (Rohu) from Halda river, Bangladesh AUGUTUS predicted genes in FASTA format. figshare. Dataset.
- Akter, S., Asek, A. A., Bhuiyan, M. A. B., Rahman, S. S., Siddiki, A. Z., Kibria, M. M. 2021 (b). *Labeo rohita* (Rohu) from Halda river, Bangladesh PANNZER2 annotation files in Excel (xlsx) format. figshare. Dataset.
- Alam, M.S., Jahan, M., Hossain, M.M. and Islam, M.S., 2009. Population genetic structure of three major river populations of rohu, *Labeo rohita* (Cyprinidae: Cypriniformes) using microsatellite DNA markers. *Genes & Genomics*, 31(1), pp.43-51.
- Alonge, M., Lebeigle, L., Kirsche, M., Aganezov, S., Wang, X., Lippman, Z.B., Schatz, M.C., and Soyk, S., 2021. Automated assembly scaffolding elevates a new tomato system for high-throughput genome editing. *BioRxiv*.
- Altschul, S.F., Madden, T.L., Schäffer, A.A., Zhang, J., Zhang, Z., Miller, W., and Lipman, D.J., 1997. Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database search programs. *Nucleic acids research*, 25 (17), 3389–3402.
- Andrews, S., 2010. Babraham bioinformatics-FastQC a quality control tool for high throughput sequence data. URL: <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc>.
- Arick, M.A., Grover, C.E., Hsu, C.-Y., Magbanua, Z.V., Pechanova, O., Miller, E.R., Thrash, A., Youngblood, R.C., Ezzell, L., and Alam, M.S., 2022. A high-quality chromosome-level genome assembly of rohu carp, *Labeo*

- rohita, and its utilization in SNP-based exploration of gene flow and sex determination. *bioRxiv*.
- Assefa, S., Keane, T.M., Otto, T.D., Newbold, C. and Berriman, M., 2009. ABACAS: algorithm-based automatic contiguation of assembled sequences. *Bioinformatics*, 25(15), pp.1968-1969.
- Atchley, W.R., Fitch, W.M., and Bronner-Fraser, M., 1994. Molecular evolution of the MyoD family of transcription factors. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 91 (24), 11522–11526.
- Avise, J.C., Arnold, J., Ball, R.M., Bermingham, E., Lamb, T., Neigel, J.E., Reeb, C.A., and Saunders, N.C., 1987. Intraspecific phylogeography: the mitochondrial DNA bridge between population genetics and systematics. *Annual review of ecology and systematics*, 489–522.
- Azadi, M.A. and Alam, M.A.U., 2013. Ichthyofauna of the River Halda, Chittagong, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Zoology*, 41 (2), 113–133.
- Bao, W., Kojima, K.K. and Kohany, O., 2015. Repbase Update, a database of repetitive elements in eukaryotic genomes. *Mobile Dna*, 6(1), pp.1-6.
- Bao, W., Kojima, K.K., and Kohany, O., 2015. Repbase Update, a database of repetitive elements in eukaryotic genomes. *Mobile Dna*, 6 (1), 1–6.
- Bao, Z. and Eddy, S.R., 2002. Automated de novo identification of repeat sequence families in sequenced genomes. *Genome research*, 12 (8), 1269–1276.
- Bej, D., Sahoo, L., Das, S.P., Swain, S., Jayasankar, P., Das, P.C., Routray, P., Swain, S.K., Jena, J.K. and Das, P., 2012. Complete mitochondrial genome sequence of *Catla catla* and its phylogenetic consideration. *Molecular biology reports*, 39(12), pp.10347-10354.
- Benson, D.A., Cavanaugh, M., Clark, K., Karsch-Mizrachi, I., Lipman, D.J., Ostell, J., and Sayers, E.W., 2012. GenBank. *Nucleic acids research*, 41 (D1), D36–D42.
- Benson, G., 1999. Tandem repeats finder: a program to analyze DNA sequences. *Nucleic acids research*, 27 (2), 573–580.
- Benton, M.J., 2014. *Vertebrate palaeontology*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bhowmick, R., Kowtal, G., Gupta, S., Jana, R., and Tiews, K., 1987. Some observations on the *Catla* x *Calbasu* hybrid produced by hypophysation.
- Bhuiyan, A.L., 1964. *Fishes of Dacca*. [1st ed.]. Dacca: Asiatic Society of Pakistan.

- Boetzer, M., Henkel, C.V., Jansen, H.J., Butler, D., and Pirovano, W., 2011. Scaffolding pre-assembled contigs using SSPACE. *Bioinformatics*, 27 (4), 578–579.
- Bolger, A.M., Lohse, M., and Usadel, B., 2014. Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics*, 30 (15), 2114–2120.
- Bonnet, E., Fostier, A., and Bobe, J., 2007. Microarray-based analysis of fish egg quality after natural or controlled ovulation. *bmc Genomics*, 8 (1), 1–17.
- Bouwman, A.C., Daetwyler, H.D., Chamberlain, A.J., Ponce, C.H., Sargolzaei, M., Schenkel, F.S., Sahana, G., Govignon-Gion, A., Boitard, S., and Dolezal, M., 2018. Meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies for cattle stature identifies common genes that regulate body size in mammals. *Nature genetics*, 50 (3), 362–367.
- Brooks, S., Tyler, C.R., and Sumpter, J.P., 1997. Egg quality in fish: what makes a good egg? *Reviews in Fish Biology and fisheries*, 7 (4), 387–416.
- Brooksbank, C., Bergman, M.T., Apweiler, R., Birney, E., and Thornton, J., 2014. The european bioinformatics institute's data resources 2014. *Nucleic acids research*, 42 (D1), D18–D25.
- Burge, C. and Karlin, S., 1997. Prediction of complete gene structures in human genomic DNA. *Journal of molecular biology*, 268 (1), 78–94.
- Burton, J.N., Adey, A., Patwardhan, R.P., Qiu, R., Kitzman, J.O., and Shendure, J., 2013. Chromosome-scale scaffolding of *de novo* genome assemblies based on chromatin interactions. *Nature biotechnology*, 31 (12), 1119–1125.
- Cantalapiedra, C.P., Hernández-Plaza, A., Letunic, I., Bork, P., and Huerta-Cepas, J., 2021. eggNOG-mapper v2: functional annotation, orthology assignments, and domain prediction at the metagenomic scale. *Molecular biology and evolution*, 38 (12), 5825–5829.
- Cantarel, B.L., Korf, I., Robb, S.M., Parra, G., Ross, E., Moore, B., Holt, C., Alvarado, A.S., and Yandell, M., 2008. MAKER: an easy-to-use annotation pipeline designed for emerging model organism genomes. *Genome research*, 18 (1), 188–196.
- Carvalho, G.R., 1993. Evolutionary aspects of fish distribution: genetic variability and adaptation. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 43 (sa), 53–73.
- Chen, N., 2004. Using Repeat Masker to identify repetitive elements in genomic sequences. *Current protocols in bioinformatics*, 5 (1), 4–10.

- Chen, S., Zhou., Y., Chen, Y., and Gu, J.(2018). Fastp: an Ultra-fast All-In-One FASTQ Preprocessor. *Bioinformatics*, 34(17), pp.i884-i890.
- Chen, Y., Chen, Y., Shi, C., Huang, Z., Zhang, Y., Li, S., Li, Y., Ye, J., Yu, C., and Li, Z., 2018. SOAPnuke: a MapReduce acceleration-supported software for integrated quality control and preprocessing of high-throughput sequencing data. *Gigascience*, 7 (1), gix120.
- Chin, C.-S., Alexander, D.H., Marks, P., Klammer, A.A., Drake, J., Heiner, C., Clum, A., Copeland, A., Huddleston, J., and Eichler, E.E., 2013. Nonhybrid, finished microbial genome assemblies from long-read SMRT sequencing data. *Nature methods*, 10 (6), 563–569.
- Complex Trait Consortium, 2003. The nature and identification of quantitative trait loci: a community’s view. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 4 (11), 911–916.
- Conesa, A., Götz, S., García-Gómez, J.M., Terol, J., Talón, M., and Robles, M., 2005. Blast2GO: a universal tool for annotation, visualization and analysis in functional genomics research. *Bioinformatics*, 21 (18), 3674–3676.
- Cortesi, F., Musilová, Z., Stieb, S.M., Hart, N.S., Siebeck, U.E., Malmstrøm, M., Tørresen, O.K., Jentoft, S., Cheney, K.L., Marshall, N.J., Carleton, K.L., and Salzburger, W., 2015. Ancestral duplications and highly dynamic opsin gene evolution in percomorph fishes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112 (5), 1493–1498.
- Cremer, M., Küpper, K., Wagler, B., Wizelman, L., Hase, J. v, Weiland, Y., Kreja, L., Diebold, J., Speicher, M.R., and Cremer, T., 2003. Inheritance of gene density–related higher order chromatin arrangements in normal and tumor cell nuclei. *The Journal of cell biology*, 162 (5), 809–820.
- Darlington, C., 1932. Recent advances in cytology pp. 559. *Philadelphia: P. Blakiston’s Son and Co.*
- Davenport, J. and Sayer, M.D.J., 1993. Physiological determinants of distribution in fish. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 43 (sa), 121–145.
- De Coster, W., D’hert, S., Schultz, D.T., Cruts, M., and Van Broeckhoven, C., 2018. NanoPack: visualizing and processing long-read sequencing data. *Bioinformatics*, 34 (15), 2666–2669.
- Delcher, A.L., Kasif, S., Fleischmann, R.D., Peterson, J., White, O., and Salzberg, S.L., 1999. Alignment of whole genomes. *Nucleic acids research*, 27 (11), 2369–2376.
- Department of Fisheries, 2018. Yearbook of fisheries statistics of Bangladesh 2017–18.

- Devlin, R.H., Biagi, C.A., Yesaki, T.Y., Smailus, D.E., and Byatt, J.C., 2001. Growth of domesticated transgenic fish. *Nature*, 409 (6822), 781–782.
- Dillon, N. and Festenstein, R., 2002. Unravelling heterochromatin: competition between positive and negative factors regulates accessibility. *TRENDS in Genetics*, 18 (5), 252–258.
- Ding, W., Zhang, X., Zhao, X., Jing, W., Cao, Z., Li, J., Huang, Y., You, X., Wang, M., and Shi, Q., 2021. A chromosome-level genome assembly of the Mandarin fish (*Siniperca chuatsi*). *Frontiers in genetics*, 12, 671650.
- DoF, 2019. *Yearbook of Fisheries Statistics of Bangladesh, 2018-19*. Department of Fisheries, Bangladesh: Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, 2020.
- DoF, 2020. *Yearbook of Fisheries Statistics of Bangladesh, 2019-20*. Fisheries Resources Survey System (FRSS), Department of Fisheries. Bangladesh: Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, 2020.
- Drmanac, R., Sparks, A.B., Callow, M.J., Halpern, A.L., Burns, N.L., Kermani, B.G., Carnevali, P., Nazarenko, I., Nilsen, G.B., and Yeung, G., 2010. Human genome sequencing using unchained base reads on self-assembling DNA nanoarrays. *Science*, 327 (5961), 78–81.
- Dudchenko, O., Batra, S.S., Omer, A.D., Nyquist, S.K., Hoeger, M., Durand, N.C., Shamim, M.S., Machol, I., Lander, E.S., and Aiden, A.P., 2017. De novo assembly of the *Aedes aegypti* genome using Hi-C yields chromosome-length scaffolds. *Science*, 356 (6333), 92–95.
- Dunham, R.A., 2011. *Aquaculture and fisheries biotechnology: genetic approaches*. 2nd ed. Wallingford, Oxfordshire, UK: CABI.
- Durand, N.C., Shamim, M.S., Machol, I., Rao, S.S., Huntley, M.H., Lander, E.S., and Aiden, E.L., 2016. Juicer provides a one-click system for analyzing loop-resolution Hi-C experiments. *Cell systems*, 3 (1), 95–98.
- Edgar, R.C. and Myers, E.W., 2005. PILER: identification and classification of genomic repeats. *Bioinformatics*, 21 (suppl_1), i152–i158.
- Egecioglu, D. and Brickner, J.H., 2011. Gene positioning and expression. *Current opinion in cell biology*, 23 (3), 338–345.
- Eid, J., Fehr, A., Gray, J., Luong, K., Lyle, J., Otto, G., Peluso, P., Rank, D., Baybayan, P., and Bettman, B., 2009. Real-time DNA sequencing from single polymerase molecules. *Science*, 323 (5910), 133–138.

- FAO, 2022. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2022. Towards Blue Transformation.
- Fishbase, 2022 [online], 2022. Available from: <https://www.fishbase.de/home.htm> [Accessed 3 Oct 2022].
- Flicek, P. and Birney, E., 2009. Sense from sequence reads: methods for alignment and assembly. *Nature methods*, 6 (11), S6–S12.
- Flicek, P., Amode, M.R., Barrell, D., Beal, K., Billis, K., Brent, S., Carvalho-Silva, D., Clapham, P., Coates, G., and Fitzgerald, S., 2014. Ensembl 2014. *Nucleic acids research*, 42 (D1), D749–D755.
- Flynn, J.M., Hubley, R., Goubert, C., Rosen, J., Clark, A.G., Feschotte, C., and Smit, A.F., 2020. RepeatModeler2 for automated genomic discovery of transposable element families. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117 (17), 9451–9457.
- Forey, P. and Janvier, P., 1994. Evolution of the early vertebrates. *American Scientist*, 82, 554.
- Frankham, R., Ballou, S.E.J.D., Briscoe, D.A., and Ballou, J.D., 2002. *Introduction to conservation genetics*. Cambridge university press.
- Friedman, M. and Sallan, L.C., 2012. Five hundred million years of extinction and recovery: a Phanerozoic survey of large-scale diversity patterns in fishes. *Palaeontology*, 55 (4), 707–742.
- Froese, R. and Pauly, D., 2002. FishBase: a global information system on fishes. *World Wide Web electronic publication: www.fishbase.org.*, 000–000.
- Gao, J., Xu, G., and Xu, P., 2021b. Whole-genome resequencing of three *Coilia nasus* population reveals genetic variations in genes related to immune, vision, migration, and osmoregulation. *BMC genomics*, 22 (1), 1–15.
- Gao, J., Xu, G., and Xu, P., 2021b. Whole-genome resequencing of three *Coilia nasus* population reveals genetic variations in genes related to immune, vision, migration, and osmoregulation. *BMC genomics*, 22 (1), 1–15.
- Gao, L., He, C., Liu, X., Su, H., Gao, X., Li, Y., and Liu, W., 2012. The innate immune-related genes in catfish. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 13 (11), 14172–14202.
- Gao, Z., You, X., Zhang, X., Chen, J., Xu, T., Huang, Y., Lin, X., Xu, J., Bian, C., and Shi, Q., 2021a. A chromosome-level genome assembly of the striped catfish (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*). *Genomics*, 113 (5), 3349–3356.

- Geldermann, H., 1975. Investigations on inheritance of quantitative characters in animals by gene markers I. Methods. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*, 46 (7), 319–330.
- Gertz, E.M., Yu, Y.-K., Agarwala, R., Schäffer, A.A., and Altschul, S.F., 2006. Composition-based statistics and translated nucleotide searches: improving the TBLASTN module of BLAST. *BMC biology*, 4 (1), 1–14.
- Ghosh, S. and Chan, C.-K.K., 2016. Analysis of RNA-Seq data using TopHat and Cufflinks. *In: Plant bioinformatics*. Springer, 339–361.
- Ghurye, J., Rhie, A., Walenz, B.P., Schmitt, A., Selvaraj, S., Pop, M., Phillippy, A.M., and Koren, S., 2019. Integrating Hi-C links with assembly graphs for chromosome-scale assembly. *PLoS computational biology*, 15 (8), e1007273.
- Goll, D.E., Thompson, V.F., Li, H., Wei, W., and Cong, J., 2003. The calpain system. *Physiological reviews*.
- Green, P., Falls, K., and Crooks, S., 1990. Documentation for CRI-MAP, version 2.4. *Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO*.
- Griffiths, J.F., Griffiths, A.J., Wessler, S.R., Lewontin, R.C., Gelbart, W.M., Suzuki, D.T., and Miller, J.H., 2005. *An introduction to genetic analysis*. Macmillan.
- Gurevich, A., Saveliev, V., Vyahhi, N., and Tesler, G., 2013. QUAST: quality assessment tool for genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics*, 29 (8), 1072–1075.
- Helfman, G.S., 2009. *The diversity of fishes: biology, evolution, and ecology*. 2nd ed. Chichester, UK: Blackwell.
- Holley, R.W., Apgar, J., Everett, G.A., Madison, J.T., Marquisee, M., Merrill, S.H., Penswick, J.R., and Zamir, A., 1965. Structure of a ribonucleic acid. *Science*, 147 (3664), 1462–1465.
- Holt, C. and Yandell, M., 2011. MAKER2: an annotation pipeline and genome-database management tool for second-generation genome projects. *BMC bioinformatics*, 12 (1), 1–14.
- Hossain, M., 1970. Marine and freshwater fishes of the Northeast part of Bay of Bengal. *Research*, 7, 26–55.
- Houston, R.D., Haley, C.S., Hamilton, A., Guy, D.R., Tinch, A.E., Taggart, J.B., McAndrew, B.J., and Bishop, S.C., 2008. Major quantitative trait loci affect resistance to infectious pancreatic necrosis in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*). *Genetics*, 178 (2), 1109–1115.

- Hu, Z.-L., Park, C.A., and Reecy, J.M., 2019. Building a livestock genetic and genomic information knowledgebase through integrative developments of Animal QTLdb and CorrDB. *Nucleic acids research*, 47 (D1), D701–D710.
- Huang, Y., Mustapha, U.F., Huang, Y., Tian, C., Yang, W., Chen, H., Deng, S., Zhu, C., Jiang, D., and Li, G., 2021. A Chromosome—Level Genome Assembly of the Spotted Scat (*Scatophagus argus*). *Genome biology and evolution*, 13 (6), evab092.
- Innan, H. and Kondrashov, F., 2010. The evolution of gene duplications: classifying and distinguishing between models. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 11 (2), 97–108.
- Jackman, S.D., Vandervalk, B.P., Mohamadi, H., Chu, J., Yeo, S., Hammond, S.A., Jahesh, G., Khan, H., Coombe, L., Warren, R.L. and Birol, I., 2017. ABySS 2.0: resource-efficient assembly of large genomes using a Bloom filter. *Genome research*, 27(5), pp.768-777.
- Jhingran, V.G. and Pullin, R.S., 1985. A hatchery manual for the common, Chinese, and Indian major carps (No. 252). WorldFish.
- Kabir, H., Kibria, M., Jashimuddin, M., and Hossain, M.M., 2015. Conservation of a river for biodiversity and ecosystem services: the case of the Halda—the unique river of Chittagong, Bangladesh. *International Journal of River Basin Management*, 13 (3), 333–342.
- Kabir, M.H., Kibria, M.M., Jashimuddin, M., and Hossain, M.M., 2013. Economic valuation of tangible resources from Halda-the carp spawning unique river located at southern part of Bangladesh. *Int J Water Res*, 1, 30–36.
- Kajitani, R., Toshimoto, K., Noguchi, H., Toyoda, A., Ogura, Y., Okuno, M., Yabana, M., Harada, M., Nagayasu, E., Maruyama, H. and Kohara, Y., 2014. Efficient de novo assembly of highly heterozygous genomes from whole-genome shotgun short reads. *Genome research*, 24(8), pp.1384-1395.
- Karl, S.A. and Avise, J.C., 1993. PCR-based assays of mendelian polymorphisms from anonymous single-copy nuclear DNA: techniques and applications for population genetics. *Molecular biology and evolution*, 10 (2), 342–361.
- Keilwagen, J., Wenk, M., Erickson, J.L., Schattat, M.H., Grau, J., and Hartung, F., 2016. Using intron position conservation for homology-based gene prediction. *Nucleic acids research*, 44 (9), e89–e89.

- Khatun, N., Islam, M.T., Sultana, N., Mrong, S. and Huq, M.A., 2017. Present status of carp hatchery and breeding operations in Bangladesh: A review. *Research in Agriculture Livestock and Fisheries*, 4(2), pp.123-129.
- Kim, D., Langmead, B., and Salzberg, S.L., 2015. HISAT: a fast spliced aligner with low memory requirements. *Nature methods*, 12 (4), 357–360.
- Knott, S., Elsen, J., and Haley, C., 1994. Multiple marker mapping of quantitative trait loci in half sib populations. Presented at the Proc. 5th World Congr. Genet. Appl. Livest. Prod., Guelph, Canada, 33–36.
- Kondrashov, F.A. and Kondrashov, A.S., 2006. Role of selection in fixation of gene duplications. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 239 (2), 141–151.
- Kondrashov, F.A., Rogozin, I.B., Wolf, Y.I., and Koonin, E.V., 2002. Selection in the evolution of gene duplications. *Genome biology*, 3 (2), 1–9.
- Koren, S., Harhay, G.P., Smith, T.P., Bono, J.L., Harhay, D.M., Mcvey, S.D., Radune, D., Bergman, N.H., and Phillippy, A.M., 2013. Reducing assembly complexity of microbial genomes with single-molecule sequencing. *Genome biology*, 14 (9), 1–16.
- Koren, S., Walenz, B.P., Berlin, K., Miller, J.R., Bergman, N.H., and Phillippy, A.M., 2017. Canu: scalable and accurate long-read assembly via adaptive k-mer weighting and repeat separation. *Genome research*, 27 (5), 722–736.
- Kosuge, T., Mashima, J., Kodama, Y., Fujisawa, T., Kaminuma, E., Ogasawara, O., Okubo, K., Takagi, T., and Nakamura, Y., 2014. DDBJ progress report: a new submission system for leading to a correct annotation. *Nucleic acids research*, 42 (D1), D44–D49.
- Lagler, K.F., 1977. *Ichthyology*. 2d ed. New York: Wiley.
- Lamond, A.I. and Spector, D.L., 2003. Nuclear speckles: a model for nuclear organelles. *Nature reviews Molecular cell biology*, 4 (8), 605–612.
- Langdon, W.B., 2015. Performance of genetic programming optimised Bowtie2 on genome comparison and analytic testing (GCAT) benchmarks. *BioData mining*, 8 (1), 1–7.
- Langmead, B. and Salzberg, S.L., 2012. Fast gapped-read alignment with Bowtie 2. *Nature methods*, 9 (4), 357–359.
- Lappalainen, T., Sammeth, M., Friedländer, M.R., t Hoen, P.A., Monlong, J., Rivas, M.A., Gonzalez-Porta, M., Kurbatova, N., Griebel, T., and Ferreira, P.G., 2013. Transcriptome and genome sequencing uncovers functional variation in humans. *Nature*, 501 (7468), 506–511.

- Leamon, J.H. and Rothberg, J.M., 2007. Cramming more sequencing reactions onto microreactor chips. *Chemical Reviews*, 107 (8), 3367–3376.
- Lesk, A.M., 2017. *Introduction to genomics*. Oxford University Press.
- Li, D., Liu, C.M., Luo, R., Sadakane, K. and Lam, T.W., 2015. MEGAHIT: an ultra-fast single-node solution for large and complex metagenomics assembly via succinct de Bruijn graph. *Bioinformatics*, 31(10), pp.1674-1676.
- Li, H. and Durbin, R., 2009. Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows–Wheeler transform. *bioinformatics*, 25 (14), 1754–1760.
- Li, H., 2013. Aligning sequence reads, clone sequences and assembly contigs with BWA-MEM. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1303.3997*.
- Li, H., 2015. BFC: correcting Illumina sequencing errors. *Bioinformatics*, 31(17), pp.2885-2887.
- Li, H., 2018. Minimap2: pairwise alignment for nucleotide sequences. *Bioinformatics*, 34 (18), 3094–3100.
- Li, H., Handsaker, B., Wysoker, A., Fennell, T., Ruan, J., Homer, N., Marth, G., Abecasis, G., and Durbin, R., 2009. The sequence alignment/map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics*, 25 (16), 2078–2079.
- Liu, D., Ma, C., Hong, W., Huang, L., Liu, M., Liu, H., Zeng, H., Deng, D., Xin, H., and Song, J., 2014. Construction and analysis of high-density linkage map using high-throughput sequencing data. *Plos one*, 9 (6), e98855.
- Lonsdale, J., Thomas, J., Salvatore, M., Phillips, R., Lo, E., Shad, S., Hasz, R., Walters, G., Garcia, F., and Young, N., 2013. The genotype-tissue expression (GTEx) project. *Nature genetics*, 45 (6), 580–585.
- Luo, R., Liu, B., Xie, Y., Li, Z., Huang, W., Yuan, J., He, G., Chen, Y., Pan, Q., and Liu, Y., 2012. SOAPdenovo2: an empirically improved memory-efficient short-read de novo assembler. *Gigascience*, 1 (1), 2047–217X.
- Luo, R., Liu, B., Xie, Y., Li, Z., Huang, W., Yuan, J., He, G., Chen, Y., Pan, Q., Liu, Y. and Tang, J., 2012. SOAPdenovo2: an empirically improved memory-efficient short-read de novo assembler. *Gigascience*, 1(1), pp.2047-217X.
- Lv, W., Zheng, X., Kuang, Y., Cao, D., Yan, Y., and Sun, X., 2016. QTL variations for growth-related traits in eight distinct families of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *BMC genetics*, 17 (1), 1–12.

- Ma, A., Huang, Z., Wang, X., Xu, Y., and Guo, X., 2021. Identification of quantitative trait loci associated with upper temperature tolerance in turbot, *Scophthalmus maximus*. *Scientific reports*, 11 (1), 1–12.
- Maclean, N. and Talwar, S., 1984. Injection of cloned genes into rainbow trout eggs. *Journal of Embryology and Experimental Morphology*, 82 (5), 187–200.
- Mallatt, J., 1984. Feeding ecology of the earliest vertebrates. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 82 (3), 261–272.
- Marçais, G. and Kingsford, C., 2011. A fast, lock-free approach for efficient parallel counting of occurrences of k-mers. *Bioinformatics*, 27 (6), 764–770.
- Martinez, R., Estrada, M.P., Berlanga, J., Guillén, I., Hernández, O., Cabrera, E., Pimentel, R., Morales, R., Herrera, F., and Morales, A., 1996. Growth enhancement in transgenic tilapia by ectopic expression of tilapia growth hormone. *Molecular marine biology and biotechnology*, 5, 62–70.
- McPherron, A.C., Lawler, A.M., and Lee, S.-J., 1997. Regulation of skeletal muscle mass in mice by a new TGF- β superfamily member. *Nature*, 387 (6628), 83–90.
- Merriman, B., R&D Team, I.T., and Rothberg, J.M., 2012. Progress in ion torrent semiconductor chip based sequencing. *Electrophoresis*, 33 (23), 3397–3417.
- Miller, W., Makova, K.D., Nekrutenko, A., and Hardison, R.C., 2004. Comparative genomics. *Annu. Rev. Genomics Hum. Genet.*, 5, 15–56.
- Mohanty, B.P., Ganguly, S., Mahanty, A., Sankar, T., Anandan, R., Chakraborty, K., Paul, B., Sarma, D., Syama Dayal, J., and Venkateshwarlu, G., 2016. DHA and EPA content and fatty acid profile of 39 food fishes from India. *BioMed Research International*, 2016.
- Mookerjee, H.K. Gupta, S.M., Chaudhury, P.K.R. 1946. Food and its percentage composition of the common adult fishes of Bengal. *Sci. Cult.* 12: 247-249.
- Moyle, P.B. and Cech, J.J., 2004. *Fishes: an introduction to ichthyology*. 5th ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Musilova, Z., Salzburger, W., and Cortesi, F., 2021. The visual opsin gene repertoires of teleost fishes: evolution, ecology, and function. *Annual Review of Cell and Developmental Biology*, 37, 441–468.
- Naruse, K., Tanaka, M., Mita, K., Shima, A., Postlethwait, J., and Mitani, H., 2004. A medaka gene map: the trace of ancestral vertebrate proto-

- chromosomes revealed by comparative gene mapping. *Genome research*, 14 (5), 820–828.
- Naser, M. N., 2015. *Labeo rohita*. In: IUCN Bangladesh. Red List of Bangladesh Volume 5: Freshwater Fishes. IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature, Bangladesh Country Office, Dhaka, Bangladesh. pp. 190.
- Near, T.J., Eytan, R.I., Dornburg, A., Kuhn, K.L., Moore, J.A., Davis, M.P., Wainwright, P.C., Friedman, M., and Smith, W.L., 2012. Resolution of ray-finned fish phylogeny and timing of diversification. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109 (34), 13698–13703.
- Nelson, J.S., 1994. *Fishes of the world*. 3. ed. New York, NY: Wiley.
- Ogasawara, O., Mashima, J., Kodama, Y., Kaminuma, E., Nakamura, Y., Okubo, K., and Takagi, T., 2012. DDBJ new system and service refactoring. *Nucleic acids research*, 41 (D1), D25–D29.
- Ohno, S., 1970. *Evolution by gene duplication*. Berlin: Springer-Verlag.
- Pakseresht, N., Alako, B., Amid, C., Cerdeño-Tárraga, A., Cleland, I., Gibson, R., Goodgame, N., Gur, T., Jang, M., and Kay, S., 2014. Assembly information services in the European Nucleotide Archive. *Nucleic acids research*, 42 (D1), D38–D43.
- Parra, G., Bradnam, K., and Korf, I., 2007. CEGMA: a pipeline to accurately annotate core genes in eukaryotic genomes. *Bioinformatics*, 23 (9), 1061–1067.
- Patra, R.W. and Azadi, M.A., 1985. Hydrological conditions influencing the spawning of major carps in the Halda River, Chittagong, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Zoology*, 13(1), pp.63-72.
- Peters, B.A., Kermani, B.G., Sparks, A.B., Alferov, O., Hong, P., Alexeev, A., Jiang, Y., Dahl, F., Tang, Y.T., and Haas, J., 2012. Accurate whole-genome sequencing and haplotyping from 10 to 20 human cells. *Nature*, 487 (7406), 190–195.
- Phillips, D.J. and de Kretser, D.M., 1998. Follistatin: a multifunctional regulatory protein. *Frontiers in neuroendocrinology*, 19 (4), 287–322.
- Price, A.L., Jones, N.C., and Pevzner, P.A., 2005. De novo identification of repeat families in large genomes. *Bioinformatics*, 21 (suppl_1), i351–i358.
- Quevillon, E., Silventoinen, V., Pillai, S., Harte, N., Mulder, N., Apweiler, R., and Lopez, R., 2005. InterProScan: protein domains identifier. *Nucleic acids research*, 33 (suppl_2), W116–W120.

- Rahman, A., 1989. Freshwater fishes of Bangladesh (pp. 364). *Dhaka, Bangladesh: Zoological Society of Bangladesh, Department of Zoology, University of Dhaka.*
- Rahman, A.A., 2005. *Freshwater fishes of Bangladesh*. 2nd edition. Zoological Society of Bangladesh.
- Rahman, A.A., 2005. Freshwater fishes of Bangladesh. Zoological society of Bangladesh.
- Rahman, S.M., Khan, M.R., Islam, S. and Alam, S., 2009. Genetic variation of wild and hatchery populations of the catla Indian major carp (*Catla catla* Hamilton 1822: Cypriniformes, Cyprinidae) revealed by RAPD markers. *Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 32(1), pp.197-201.
- Robledo, D., Fernández, C., Hermida, M., Sciara, A., Álvarez-Dios, J.A., Cabaleiro, S., Caamaño, R., Martínez, P., and Bouza, C., 2016. Integrative transcriptome, genome and quantitative trait loci resources identify single nucleotide polymorphisms in candidate genes for growth traits in turbot. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 17 (2), 243.
- Rolland, A.D., Lareyre, J.-J., Goupil, A.-S., Montfort, J., Ricordel, M.-J., Esquerré, D., Hugot, K., Houlgatte, R., Chalmel, F., and Le Gac, F., 2009. Expression profiling of rainbow trout testis development identifies evolutionary conserved genes involved in spermatogenesis. *Bmc Genomics*, 10 (1), 1–22.
- Rose, P.W., Bi, C., Bluhm, W.F., Christie, C.H., Dimitropoulos, D., Dutta, S., Green, R.K., Goodsell, D.S., Prlić, A., and Quesada, M., 2012. The RCSB Protein Data Bank: new resources for research and education. *Nucleic acids research*, 41 (D1), D475–D482.
- Ruan, J. and Li, H., 2020. Fast and accurate long-read assembly with wtdbg2. *Nature methods*, 17 (2), 155–158.
- Sakmar, T.P., Menon, S.T., Marin, E.P., and Awad, E.S., 2002. Rhodopsin: insights from recent structural studies. *Annual review of biophysics and biomolecular structure*, 31 (1), 443–484.
- Salmela, L. and Rivals, E., 2014. LoRDEC: accurate and efficient long read error correction. *Bioinformatics*, 30 (24), 3506–3514.
- Sanger, F., Nicklen, S., and Coulson, A.R., 1977. DNA sequencing with chain-terminating inhibitors. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 74 (12), 5463–5467.

- Sayers, E.W., Cavanaugh, M., Clark, K., Pruitt, K.D., Sherry, S.T., Yankie, L., and Karsch-Mizrachi, I., 2022. GenBank 2023 update. *Nucleic Acids Research*.
- Schneider, M., Consortium, the U., and Poux, S., 2012. UniProtKB amid the turmoil of plant proteomics research. *Frontiers in plant science*, 3, 270.
- Seaton, G., Haley, C.S., Knott, S.A., Kearsey, M., and Visscher, P.M., 2002. QTL Express: mapping quantitative trait loci in simple and complex pedigrees. *Bioinformatics*, 18 (2), 339–340.
- Seebens, H., Blackburn, T.M., Dyer, E.E., Genovesi, P., Hulme, P.E., Jeschke, J.M., Pagad, S., Pyšek, P., Winter, M., and Arianoutsou, M., 2017. No saturation in the accumulation of alien species worldwide. *Nature communications*, 8 (1), 1–9.
- Seppey, M., Manni, M. and Zdobnov, E.M., 2019. BUSCO: assessing genome assembly and annotation completeness. *Methods in molecular biology* (Clifton, NJ), 1962, pp.227-245.
- Seppey, M., Manni, M., and Zdobnov, E.M., 2019. BUSCO: assessing genome assembly and annotation completeness. *In: Gene prediction*. Springer, 227–245.
- Shivji, M., Clarke, S., Pank, M., Natanson, L., Kohler, N., and Stanhope, M., 2002. Genetic identification of pelagic shark body parts for conservation and trade monitoring. *Conservation Biology*, 16 (4), 1036–1047.
- Shrestha, J., 1994. Fishes, fishing implements and methods of Nepal.
- Silva, L.D.C.E., Wang, S., and Zeng, Z.-B., 2012. Composite interval mapping and multiple interval mapping: procedures and guidelines for using Windows QTL Cartographer. *In: Quantitative trait loci (QTL)*. Springer, 75–119.
- Simão, F.A., Waterhouse, R.M., Ioannidis, P., Kriventseva, E.V., and Zdobnov, E.M., 2015. BUSCO: assessing genome assembly and annotation completeness with single-copy orthologs. *Bioinformatics*, 31 (19), 3210–3212.
- Simonsen V, Hansen MM, Mensberg KLD, Sarder RI and Alam S. 2005. Wide spread hybridization among species of Indian major carps in hatcheries, but not in the wild. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 67:794-808.
- Smit, A., Hubley, R., and Green, P., 2013. 2015 RepeatMasker Open-4.0.

- Smit, A.F.A., Hubley, R. and Green, P., 2015. RepeatMasker Open-4.0. 2013–2015.
- Smith, B.D., Ahmed, B., Ali, M.E., and Braulik, G., 2001. Status of the Ganges river dolphin or shushuk *Platanista gangetica* in Kaptai Lake and the southern rivers of Bangladesh. *Oryx*, 35 (1), 61–72.
- Stanford, C.B., 1991. *The capped langur in Bangladesh: behavioral ecology and reproductive tactics*. Karger Medical and Scientific Publishers.
- Stanke, M. and Morgenstern, B., 2005. AUGUSTUS: a web server for gene prediction in eukaryotes that allows user-defined constraints. *Nucleic acids research*, 33(suppl_2), pp.W465-W467.
- Stanke, M. and Waack, S., 2003. Gene prediction with a hidden Markov model and a new intron submodel. *Bioinformatics*, 19 (suppl_2), ii215–ii225.
- Stanke, M., Diekhans, M., Baertsch, R., and Haussler, D., 2008. Using native and syntenically mapped cDNA alignments to improve de novo gene finding. *Bioinformatics*, 24 (5), 637–644.
- Stanke, M., Steinkamp, R., Waack, S., and Morgenstern, B., 2004. AUGUSTUS: a web server for gene finding in eukaryotes. *Nucleic acids research*, 32 (suppl_2), W309–W312.
- Su, G.-S., Liljedahl, L.-E., and Gall, G.A., 1997. Genetic and environmental variation of female reproductive traits in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Aquaculture*, 154 (2), 115–124.
- Sun, L., Gao, T., Wang, F., Qin, Z., Yan, L., Tao, W., Li, M., Jin, C., Ma, L., and Kocher, T.D., 2020. Chromosome-level genome assembly of a cyprinid fish *Onychostoma macrolepis* by integration of nanopore sequencing, Bionano and Hi-C technology. *Molecular ecology resources*, 20 (5), 1361–1371.
- Talwar, P.K. and Jhingran, A.G., 1991. *Inland fishes of India and adjacent countries*. CRC Press.
- Tang, H., Zhang, X., Miao, C., Zhang, J., Ming, R., Schnable, J.C., Schnable, P.S., Lyons, E., and Lu, J., 2015. ALLMAPS: robust scaffold ordering based on multiple maps. *Genome biology*, 16 (1), 1–15.
- Törönen, P., Medlar, A. and Holm, L., 2018. PANNZER2: a rapid functional annotation web server. *Nucleic acids research*, 46(W1), pp.W84-W88.
- Trapnell, C., Pachter, L., and Salzberg, S.L., 2009. TopHat: discovering splice junctions with RNA-Seq. *Bioinformatics*, 25 (9), 1105–1111.

- Tsai, C.-F., Nazrul Islam, M., Karim, R., and Shahidur Rahman, K., 1981. Spawning of major carps in the lower Halda River, Bangladesh. *Estuaries*, 4 (2), 127–138.
- Tsai, C.F., Islam, M.N., Karim, R. and Rahman, K.S., 1981. Spawning of major carps in the lower Halda River, Bangladesh. *Estuaries*, 4(2), pp.127-138.
- Ulloa, P.E., Iturra, P., Neira, R., and Araneda, C., 2011. Zebrafish as a model organism for nutrition and growth: towards comparative studies of nutritional genomics applied to aquacultured fishes. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries*, 21 (4), 649–666.
- Van Driel, R., Fransz, P.F., and Verschure, P.J., 2003. The eukaryotic genome: a system regulated at different hierarchical levels. *Journal of cell science*, 116 (20), 4067–4075.
- Vaser, R., Sović, I., Nagarajan, N., and Šikić, M., 2017. Fast and accurate de novo genome assembly from long uncorrected reads. *Genome research*, 27 (5), 737–746.
- Volkoff, H., 2016. The neuroendocrine regulation of food intake in fish: a review of current knowledge. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, 10, 540.
- Wagner, A., 2008. Gene duplications, robustness and evolutionary innovations. *Bioessays*, 30 (4), 367–373.
- Waldeyer, W., 1888. Über Karyokinese und ihre Beziehungen zu den Befruchtungsvorgängen. *Archiv für mikroskopische Anatomie*, 32 (1), 1–122.
- Walker, B.J., Abeel, T., Shea, T., Priest, M., Abouelliel, A., Sakthikumar, S., Cuomo, C.A., Zeng, Q., Wortman, J., and Young, S.K., 2014. Pilon: an integrated tool for comprehensive microbial variant detection and genome assembly improvement. *PloS one*, 9 (11), e112963.
- Woodcock, C.L., 2006. Chromatin architecture. *Current opinion in structural biology*, 16 (2), 213–220.
- Wringe, B.F., Devlin, R.H., Ferguson, M.M., Moghadam, H.K., Sakhrani, D., and Danzmann, R.G., 2010. Growth-related quantitative trait loci in domestic and wild rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *BMC genetics*, 11 (1), 1–14.
- Wu, T.D. and Watanabe, C.K., 2005. GMAP: a genomic mapping and alignment program for mRNA and EST sequences. *Bioinformatics*, 21 (9), 1859–1875.
- Xiao, C.-L., Chen, Y., Xie, S.-Q., Chen, K.-N., Wang, Y., Han, Y., Luo, F., and Xie, Z., 2017. MECAT: fast mapping, error correction, and de novo

- assembly for single-molecule sequencing reads. *nature methods*, 14 (11), 1072–1074.
- Xie, Z., Wang, D., Jiang, S., Peng, C., Wang, Q., Huang, C., Li, S., Lin, H., and Zhang, Y., 2022. Chromosome-Level Genome Assembly and Transcriptome Comparison Analysis of *Cephalopholis sonnerati* and Its Related Grouper Species. *Biology*, 11 (7), 1053.
- Xu, J., Zhao, Z., Zhang, X., Zheng, X., Li, J., Jiang, Y., Kuang, Y., Zhang, Y., Feng, J., and Li, C., 2014. Development and evaluation of the first high-throughput SNP array for common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *BMC genomics*, 15 (1), 1–10.
- Xu, Z. and Wang, H., 2007. LTR_FINDER: an efficient tool for the prediction of full-length LTR retrotransposons. *Nucleic acids research*, 35 (suppl_2), W265–W268.
- Yassumoto, T.I., Nakatsukasa, M., Nagano, A.J., Yasugi, M., Yoshimura, T., and Shinomiya, A., 2020. Genetic analysis of body weight in wild populations of medaka fish from different latitudes. *PLOS ONE*, 15 (6), e0234803.
- Yi, S. and Streebman, J.T., 2005. Genome size is negatively correlated with effective population size in ray-finned fish. *Trends in Genetics*, 21 (12), 643–646.
- Yu, H., You, X., Li, J., Liu, H., Meng, Z., Xiao, L., Zhang, H., Lin, H.-R., Zhang, Y., and Shi, Q., 2016. Genome-wide mapping of growth-related quantitative trait loci in orange-spotted grouper (*Epinephelus coioides*) using double digest restriction-site associated DNA sequencing (ddRADseq). *International journal of molecular sciences*, 17 (4), 501.
- Zhang, X., Huang, C., Wu, D., Qiao, F., Li, W., Duan, L., Wang, K., Xiao, Y., Chen, G., and Liu, Q., 2017. High-throughput phenotyping and QTL mapping reveals the genetic architecture of maize plant growth. *Plant physiology*, 173 (3), 1554–1564.
- Zhao, L., Xu, S., Han, Z., Liu, Q., Ke, W., Liu, A., and Gao, T., 2021. Chromosome-Level Genome Assembly and Annotation of a Sciaenid Fish, *Argyrosomus japonicus*. *Genome biology and evolution*, 13 (2), evaa246.
- Zhu, K., Zhang, N., Liu, B.-S., Guo, L., Guo, H.-Y., Jiang, S.-G., and Zhang, D., 2021. A chromosome-level genome assembly of the yellowfin seabream (*Acanthopagrus latus*; Hottuyn, 1782) provides insights into its osmoregulation and sex reversal. *Genomics*, 113 (4), 1617–1627.

- Zhu, K., Zhang, N., Liu, B.-S., Guo, L., Guo, H.-Y., Jiang, S.-G., and Zhang, D., 2021. A chromosome-level genome assembly of the yellowfin seabream (*Acanthopagrus latus*; Hottuyn, 1782) provides insights into its osmoregulation and sex reversal. *Genomics*, 113 (4), 1617–1627.
- Zimin, A.V., Marçais, G., Puiu, D., Roberts, M., Salzberg, S.L., and Yorke, J.A., 2013. The MaSuRCA genome assembler. *Bioinformatics*, 29 (21), 2669–2677.
- Zonaed Siddiki, A.M.A.M., Miah, G., Islam, M., Kumkum, M., Rumi, M.H., Baten, A. and Hossain, M.A., 2020. Goat genomic resources: the search for genes associated with its economic traits. *International Journal of Genomics*, 2020.